

MASTER TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISORY SKILLS AND TEACHERS PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR SCHOOL SUPERVISORY PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The Theory of Supervisory Impact on Teaching Excellence is established in this study as it posits that consistent and effective instructional supervision by Master Teachers (MTs) is fundamental in enhancing teaching performance. This study delved into the MTs instructional supervisory skills and teacher performance as basis for a school supervisory plan. Particularly, it investigated the teachers' demographic characteristics, the MT's level of supervisory skills, the teachers' teaching performance, and the significant relationship and significant difference of the variables. The study utilized a quantitative research design, particularly descriptive correlational method. Through the use of Slovin's formula, the study included the 529 Master Teachers and Teachers from both elementary and secondary schools as the research respondents. The questionnaire was adopted, while other parts were adapted and modified. In analyzing the data gathered, the study used both descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson (r) correlation as statistical tools. The findings of the study revealed that teachers are mostly female, have earned units in Masters, have been in the service for 6-10 years, do not belong to any of the seven tribes of Bukidnon, and have a positive attitude towards instructional supervision. The Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills are excellent, while the teachers' teaching performance is outstanding. Meanwhile, the correlation analysis showed a positive significant correlation between Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills and the teachers' teaching performance. The regression results showed no significant difference in the teachers' teaching performance when they were grouped according to sex and ethnicity but showed significant difference when grouped according to highest educational attainment,

teaching experience, and attitude towards instructional supervision Finally, the study proposed a school supervisory plan that was designed based on the teachers' lowest indicators in their teaching performance. As a conclusion, this study found that Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills impacts teachers' performance, hence, recommends the adoption and implementation of the school instructional supervisory plan.

Keywords: *instructional supervisory skills, teaching performance*

INTRODUCTION

The role of Master Teachers (MTs) in the dynamic context of education extends beyond the classroom, encompassing a vital aspect of educational leadership - that is their instructional supervisory skills. It is a dynamic process that involves observation, feedback, and collaboration. The efficacy of master teachers in guiding and enhancing the performance of their fellow educators plays a critical role in creating an environment where continuous learning and improvement thrive.

The efficacy of master teachers in enhancing the performance of their fellow teachers is rooted in their capacity to provide constructive feedback (Dingal, 2023; Sangalang, 2018), tailored support (Gestupa, 2023; Cortez, 2023), and personalized professional development (Magcanas, 2019; Makavec, 2018). Through keen observation, master teachers identify strengths and areas for improvement, offering targeted guidance to help teachers refine their instructional techniques, classroom management strategies, and overall pedagogical approaches. This collaborative and reflective process fosters a culture of continuous improvement, where teachers feel supported and empowered to embrace innovation and refine their practice.

The trajectory of teachers' practice and performance is commonly conducted through a performance appraisal, essentially a method to gauge an individual's contributions in the field of teaching, particular to students' performance. A component of this appraisal process involves a systematic planning cycle and meticulous observation to evaluate teacher performance, which is usually done by an MT or a school principal. The expectation is that through instructional supervision, teachers receive feedback aimed at enhancing the quality of their performance. Thus, the effectiveness of a teacher's teaching performance is crucially impacted by the effectiveness of the MTs instructional supervision.

According to Kanya et al. (2021), teachers' performance is not solely determined by their instructional abilities but also by their capacity to engage with students, adapt to diverse learning styles, and foster a conducive learning environment. Makavec (2018) explained that effective teaching encompasses not only the dissemination of knowledge but also the cultivation of critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and a passion for lifelong learning. Therefore, the appraisal of teachers should encompass a comprehensive assessment of their pedagogical strategies, classroom management skills, and their

ability to establish rapport with students. Moreover, it should consider factors beyond academic achievement, such as the promotion of socio-emotional development and the integration of technology to enhance learning outcomes.

In the Philippines, the creation of master teacher positions, initially comprising four levels aligned with the pay grades of principals and assistant principals, represents their skills and experience in the field. This initiative introduced a dual-track system for career advancement among teachers, accommodating both school management and classroom teaching roles.

Previous researchers highlighted the significant role that master teachers play in terms of aiding and instructional supervision to fellow teachers. Carraway and Young (2018) posited that MTs must have enough instructional leadership which serves as a mechanism to bolster instructors' teaching practices, foster professional growth, and oversee resource management. Through coaching and mentoring, instructional leaders provide the necessary support to teachers, assisting them in the ongoing enhancement of their teaching methods. Meanwhile, Bush et al. (2018) considered MTs as the “crème del a crème” among educators as they exhibit distinct teaching methods that set them apart from regular, non-master teachers.

Despite the established roles, responsibilities, and skills of Master Teachers and their effect on teaching performance, there exists a noticeable research gap, particularly within the context of the division under study, regarding the perception of school teachers on the supervisory skills of MTs and its correlation with their teaching performance. Hence, the present study aimed to address the research gap by investigating the perspectives of public-school teachers on the master teachers' supervisory skills and how it affects their teaching performance. The study also aimed to propose a supervisory development plan that can help both teachers and master teachers.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the level of Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills and teacher's performance in the division of Valencia City for the School Year 2023-2024. The result of the study would serve as the basis for the school supervisory plan. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How are the respondents' distributed in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity, and attitude towards instructional supervision?
2. What is the level of master teacher's instructional supervisory skills based on coaching, mentoring, clinical observation, pedagogical, technological, and evaluation?
3. What is the level of teachers' performance with regard to teaching and learning process, students' outcome, community involvement, professional growth and development?
4. Is there a significant relationship between Master Teacher's instructional supervisory skills and the teachers' performance?

5. Is there a significant difference in the teachers' performance when grouped according to their characteristics?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what school instructional supervisory plan can be designed?

Hypothesis

Problems 1, 2, 3, and 6 were hypotheses – free. On the basis of Problems 4 and 5, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant relationship between master teacher's instructional supervisory skills and the teachers' performance.

H02: There is no significant difference in the teachers' performance when grouped according to their characteristics.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The present study utilized a quantitative research design, particularly descriptive correlational method. Descriptive correlation is a research method that aims to understand the relationship between variables without necessarily implying causation. In this approach, researchers collect data on multiple variables of interest and analyse how they relate to each other. In the present study, utilizing a quantitative research design with a descriptive correlational method allowed for the examination of the relationship between the secondary school teachers' characteristics, perceived teaching performance, and the perceived level of their Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills.

By collecting and analysing data on these variables, the study provided valuable insights into their associations, contributing to a deeper understanding and the creation of the proposed Master Teacher's Supervisory Plan that would help improved the teachers' performance in attaining quality education.

Study Setting

The present study was conducted among the four hundred seventeen (417) teachers and one hundred twelve (112) Master Teachers of the Division of Valencia City in the Province of Bukidnon. The division is composed of ten (10) school districts located in thirty-one (31) different barangays headed by Public School District Supervisor and the Education Program Supervisors (EPS) with their assigned focus to insure the quality of education and the implementation of the programs and projects so that no Valencianos are left behind. DepEd Valencia City, through its various divisions and offices, oversees the administration of public schools within its jurisdiction. This includes curriculum development, teacher hiring and training, school infrastructure development, student enrollment, and educational assessment.

The division of Valencia became the third independent School Division in the Province of Bukidnon in 1993 to cater to the growing number of schools in the City of Valencia. At present, the Division Office is home to seven secondary schools, twelve (12) elementary schools and twenty-five (25) integrated schools in the locality. It has conducted a series of training to capacitate both Master Teachers and Teachers I-III in their respective fields. The Division of Valencia City thrive for excellent, thus offers teachers' training in academic quality and teaching performance. The outcomes of this research can positively impact the educational landscape of the locale of the study that can contribute to the improvement of the broader educational system, and highlight the contributions of effective teachers and school heads, leading to professional recognition and career advancement opportunities. Figure 2 presents the map of the City of Valencia, highlighting the locations of the study.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study included five hundred twenty-five (529) teachers of elementary and secondary schools in the Division of Valencia. This diverse group of educators collectively contributed to the study's breadth and depth. By encompassing such a broad spectrum of participants, the study gained valuable insights into the multifaceted dynamics of master teachers' instructional supervisory skills and teachers' performance across different grade levels and subject areas within the educational landscape of Valencia City.

Sampling Technique

For this research, the researcher utilized the Slovin's formula to choose a sample size of 33% from the total population of teachers in the Division of Valencia City. The objective was to represent all teachers within the division with the existing master teachers assigned, ensuring each one had a recognized, non-zero probability of being selected for the sample.

The study initially gathered data regarding the total number of secondary and elementary school teachers with master teachers in the Division of Valencia City, represented as N . Moreover, the standard deviation (σ) of specific pertinent characteristics was considered, offering insights into the diversity within the teacher cohort. Additionally, the research defined the desired precision level (E), which represented the maximum acceptable margin of error for the study.

Once the sample size was established, the researcher proceeded to persuade the five hundred twenty-nine (529) teachers and master teachers from the entire population. This approach guaranteed that every teacher in the Division of Valencia had an equal opportunity to be part of the study, thereby ensuring the comprehensiveness of the sample selection. Following this, the researcher gathered and scrutinized data from these chosen teachers, enabling her to derive significant insights aligned with the research objectives. It is crucial to acknowledge that while universal non-probability sampling

promotes inclusivity, the precision of the findings hinges on the accuracy of population data and the assumption of uniformity among the teacher population in the district.

Research Instruments

To gather the necessary data, this study used two sets of questionnaires that underwent reliability testing. The first survey questionnaire was distributed to the elementary and secondary school teachers and master teachers.

Part I of this survey questionnaire included the respondent's characteristics such as their sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience and ethnicity and a questionnaire that contained indicators of teachers' attitude towards instructional supervision. The teachers' attitude towards instructional supervision was assessed using a Likert scale questionnaire adopted from Ramin (2014). It contained ten statements which the respondents had to check regarding their belief on supervision. It used a 4-point Likert scale, where 4 has the description of "Strongly Agree of what I believe," 3 for "Agree of what I believe," 2 for "Disagree of what I believe," and 1 for "Strongly Disagree of what I believe."

Part II of the questionnaire for the MTs contained statements that revolved around the components of instructional supervisory skills. It included components such as coaching, mentoring, clinical observation, pedagogical and technological evaluation. The indicators for the instructional supervisory skills were adapted and modified from the study of Laude et al. (2014). The statements in this questionnaire were modified to fit the context of the present study. To further enhance the relevance of the study, a pool of experts was consulted to review the modified statements. Their insights helped refine the adjustments and confirm that the changes were well-suited to the locale context.

Part III contained indicators of teaching performance that was also adapted and modified from Virginia Public Schools Performance Evaluation for Teachers (2016). It included areas such teaching and learning process, student's outcome, community involvement, and professional growth and development. The statements in each component were adjusted to align with the context of the study. This involved removing statements that were not relevant to the Philippine setting and replacing them with those that are appropriate and applicable. Additionally, efforts were made to ensure that the new statements maintained the original intent and meaning while being culturally and contextually suitable.

The first set of questionnaires was to assess teacher's performance. It contained Part I which is the respondent's characteristics such as their sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity, and attitude towards instructional supervision and Part III the teacher's level of teaching performance. The other set of questionnaires was to assess their instructional supervisory competence of Master Teachers. It also contained part I was for the respondent's characteristics such as their sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity, and attitude towards instructional supervision and Part II was about master teachers' supervisory skills.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The indicators on the teacher's performance were adopted from the Virginia Public Schools Performance Evaluation for Teachers (2016) while the indicators for the master teachers' supervisory skills were adopted from the study of Laude et al. (2014). Both were modified to fit the context of the present study.

To evaluate the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher asked three (3) experts in the field of education for face testing. After this, they recommend that the integrity and effectiveness of the questionnaire were relevant in capturing accurate data. It adheres to the questionnaire design principles which is likely to guarantee the appropriateness of data collection in educational research. Before it was administered, the research instrument was pilot-tested on thirty (30) teachers from the division of Bukidnon and Valencia City with the same characteristics but were not part of the respondents of the present study. The results of the pilot testing were used for validity and reliability tests.

It can be seen from the results that in the domains related to attitudes towards instructional supervision, teachers' performance, teaching and learning processes, students' outcomes, community involvement, and professional growth and development, the coefficients ranged from .779 to .897. These results suggest that the items within each of these constructs reliably measure their respective concepts, with coefficients well above the commonly accepted threshold of .70 for satisfactory reliability. Moreover, when examining the instructional supervisory skills, which encompass coaching, mentoring, clinical supervision, pedagogical knowledge, technological competence, and evaluation proficiency, the reliability coefficients were notably high, ranging from .923 to .954. The overall Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of .984 demonstrated exceptional internal consistency with an impressive overall.

Categorization of Variables

Part I. Respondents Characteristics

Sex Male

Female

Highest Educational Qualification

Doctorate Degree

Master's Degree with PhD units

Master's Degree

Bachelor's degree with Master's units

Teaching Experience

16 years and above

11-15 years

6-10 years

3-5 years

3 years and below

Ethnicity

Bukidnon
 Higaonon
 Manobo
 Matigsalog
 Talaandig
 Tigwahanon
 Umayamnon
 None of the above

System of Scoring

Attitude Towards Instructional Supervision

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.14 – 4.20	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3	2.61 – 3.40	Agree	Positive
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative

Part II. Master Teacher's Supervisory Skills

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.14 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Excellent
3	2.61 – 3.40	Agree	Average
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Below average
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Poor

Part III. Teacher's Level of Teaching Performance

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.14 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Outstanding
3	2.61 – 3.40	Agree	Very Satisfactory
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Satisfactory
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Poor

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of Graduate Studies and submitted it to the Division Office for approval to conduct the study among secondary school teachers. Once the letter request was approved, another letter request was sent to the principals of the identified schools for the same purpose of asking permission to conduct the study. Then, the researcher recruited teachers to participate in the study. The researcher personally visited the identified secondary schools and informed the teachers of the purpose and the general overview of the study. It was also reiterated to the respondents that their participation was voluntary. Hence, they could opt not to participate for whatever reason. Their decision to participate would not in any way affect their positions in the school. When the number of respondents was identified, the researcher then distributed the survey questionnaire among the respondents. It was collected after a week, and the results were tallied, and the necessary statistical treatment was performed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics were employed to outline the fundamental attributes of the data in the study, offering concise descriptions of both the sample and the measurements.

First, in identifying the respondent's characteristics in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity, and attitude towards instructional supervision, this study employed frequency and percentage as statistical tools.

Secondly, in identifying Master Teacher's instructional supervisory skills in terms of coaching, mentoring, clinical observation, pedagogical, and technological evaluation, mean and standard deviations were also used.

In the same way, when determining the teacher's level of teaching performance in terms of teaching and learning process, student's outcome, community involvement, professional growth and development, mean and standard deviations were used as statistical tools.

In ascertaining the significant relationship between the Master Teacher's instructional supervisory skills and teaching performance, Pearson r moment correlation was used as statistical tool. The same statistical tool was also used to determine the significant relationship between the teacher's teaching performance in terms of teaching and learning process, student's outcome, community involvement, professional growth and development in relation to their characteristics such as sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity and attitude towards instructional supervision

Scope and Limitations

The scope of the study included teachers in the division of Valencia City. It investigated the teacher's characteristics, their attitude towards instructional supervision, their teaching performance in terms of teaching and learning process, student's outcome, community involvement and professional growth and development. It also determined the level of Master Teacher's supervisory skills. Furthermore, the significant relationship between the teacher's teaching performance and master teacher's supervisory skills in terms of coaching, mentoring, clinical supervision, pedagogical, technological and evaluation skills was also investigated. Finally, the study recommended a master teacher supervisory plan that aimed to capacitate master teachers in assisting the secondary school teachers in improving their performance.

The present study was limited since the assessment of the teaching performance and the MTs supervisory skills was done one time. Time limitations could have limited the longitudinal aspect of the study, preventing the researcher from assessing the long-term impact of master teachers' supervisory plans on teacher performance. Additionally, the use of survey questionnaires alone as the instrument may have limited the depth of understanding. While surveys are efficient for collecting data from a large number of participants, it may not have totally captured the complex aspects of teaching performance and supervisory skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. How are the respondents distributed in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity, and attitude toward instructional supervision?

Table 1.1. Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Male	80	15.1
Female	449	84.94
Total	529	100.0

Table 1.1 depicts the statistical result of the respondents' profile in terms of sex. It shows that the majority of the study's respondents are female, which comprised 449 individuals (84.9%) of the study's population. Meanwhile, only 80 teachers are male, which constitutes the remaining 15.1% of the population. The results indicate that the teaching force of the study's locale is dominated by female teachers, reflecting a gender imbalance in the profession. This dominance could influence various aspects of the educational environment, including teaching styles, instructional supervision, and teaching performance.

The result coincides with the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2024) report that observed scarcity of male teachers in the teaching profession. The gender disparities and under-representation of men in the field of teaching are influenced by complex factors such as historical biases, societal norms, and structural barriers. According to Wong (2019), the decision to educate young children was historically entrenched as an activity associated with femininity. This perception often limited opportunities for men to enter the field and perpetuated gender stereotypes about caregiving roles.

However, Dahl (2021) explained that the teaching profession is evolving with an increasing number of men entering the field, which is traditionally female-dominated. This shift brings diverse perspectives and teaching styles, contributing to a more balanced and inclusive educational environment.

Table 1.2. Distribution of the Respondents' in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	12	2.3
Master's Degree with PhD Units	62	11.7
Master's degree	144	27.2
Bachelor's Degree with master's Unit	311	58.8
Total	529	100.0

Table 1.2 shows the distribution of the respondents in terms of highest educational attainment. It reflects that the greatest number of respondents, 311 individuals (58.8%), have earned units in Masters. Meanwhile, the lowest number of respondents are those with doctorate degree holders, which include only three teachers or 2.3% of the study's population. The overall result shows a significant commitment to higher education among the teachers, with nearly all participants engaged in or having completed postgraduate education. This implies that high percentage suggests a strong inclination towards advanced education, not necessarily at the doctoral level. This trend highlights the value placed on advanced academic credentials, particularly at the master's level, which reflects the educational requirements or professional aspirations prevalent in the division under study.

The results support the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS, 2018) report, which states that teachers' educational attainment encompasses both their pre-service training and any supplementary qualifications obtained during their tenure. The caliber and extent of their initial education significantly influence their performance upon entering the teaching profession and should inform subsequent educational pursuits and training needs (Pardillo, 2021; Ganal et al., 2019), as well as other facets of their professional growth. For instance, inadequate or substandard formal education may heighten the necessity for ongoing professional development among teachers. Conversely, a vigorous formal education background may instigate a stronger inclination towards seeking further educational and training opportunities to refine skills acquired during their extensive academic training.

On the other hand, the minimal number of respondents with units in Ph.D. or full-fledged PhDs support the claims of Rungduin and Miranda (2018) that factors such as workload and expenses are the primary reasons teachers shy away from pursuing graduate studies. Pursuing a Ph.D. while maintaining a career in education is demanding in terms of time and energy, given the rigorous academic requirements and research obligations typically associated with doctoral studies. Additionally, the financial costs involved, including tuition and research expenses, can pose significant barriers for educators, especially those with familial responsibilities or limited financial resources.

Table 1.3. Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Teaching Experience

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
16 years and above	191	36.1
11 - 15 years	113	21.4
6 – 10 years	152	28.7
3 – 5 years	46	8.7
3 years and below	27	5.1
Total	529	100.0

Table 1.3 provides the distribution of the respondents in terms of teaching experience. It explains that the highest frequency is seen in the category of teachers with 16 years and above of service, comprising 191 (36.1%) of the total respondents. This indicates a

significant portion of the teaching workforce is in their mid-career stage, suggesting a relatively stable group of experienced teachers who are likely to have developed a solid teaching practice and familiarity with the educational system. On the other hand, the lowest frequency is observed in the category of teachers with 3 years or below of service, making up only 27 individuals (5.1%) of the respondents. This low percentage implies a smaller influx of new teachers into the division, which could imply challenges in attracting new educators or a stable workforce with low turnover rates. Balancing the experience with fresh perspectives from new educators is essential for ongoing innovations and adaptability in teaching practices within the Division.

Previous research shows that experienced teachers are vital in shaping the education system and fostering the growth of students and society. For instance, Marshall (2021) claimed that teachers improve in raising student achievement as they gain experience, becoming nearly twice as effective as novices after 15 years. Furthermore, Graham et al. (2020) found that teachers with two decades or more of experience are significantly more effective than they were at the beginning of their careers.

Sharrock (2023) asserted that teachers who are in early career positions are pivotal groups for mentorship, leadership cultivation (Ma, 2022; Luftiyana & Sugito, 2020), and strategies aimed at retaining talent within educational institutions (Pardillo et al., 2021). Additionally, the results underscore the necessity for tailored support and initiatives for professional development. These endeavors are crucial for facilitating their transition into the teaching profession, fostering effective instructional techniques, and navigating the initial challenges of their careers.

Table 1.4. Distribution of the Respondents' in terms of Ethnicity

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Bukidnon	139	26.3
Higaonon	8	1.5
Manobo	21	3.9
Matigsalog	2	0.4
Talaandig	13	2.5
Tigwahanon	9	1.7
Umayamnon	1	0.2
None of the above	336	63.5
Total	529	100.0

Table 1.4 reflects the distribution of respondents in terms of ethnicity. It reveals significant diversity among the teaching staff. The largest group, constituting 336 individuals (63.5%) of the respondents, falls under the category None of the above, indicating that the majority of teachers do not identify with any of the specified indigenous ethnic groups. This reflects the broader national or regional ethnic demographics or a predominantly non-indigenous teaching workforce. On the other hand, the smallest representation is found among the Umayamnon, with only 1 individual (0.2%) of the respondents identifying as part of this group. The results corroborate the article in Bukidnon website (Bukidnon.gov.ph, 2012)

that the mixture of cultures in Bukidnon stems from the different levels of interaction and integration with outside influences. The recent immigrants add to this cultural diversity, blending their own traditions with those of Bukidnon. These dynamics create a unique cultural combination, reflecting both the preservation of indigenous traditions and the integration of modern influences.

Table 1.5. Distribution of the Respondents' Attitude Towards Instructional Supervision

Legend:

0.50-4.00	Strongly Agree/Very Positive	1.50-2.49	Disagree/Negative	
Indicators		Mean	SD	Description
Supervisor is more towards finding teachers' weaknesses.		2.85	0.94	Agree
Supervision done is trustworthy.		3.41	0.58	Agree
The supervision is aimed at sharing shared responsibilities between teachers and supervisors		3.52	0.56	Strongly Agree
Supervision is performed with the aim of control rather than upgrading.		2.76	0.94	Agree
Supervision is an examination and not a cooperation process.		2.67	0.93	Agree
Supervision creates excitement for teachers.		2.97	0.79	Agree
Supervision focuses heavily on teachers.		2.94	0.80	Agree
Supervision is a supportive process aimed at professional growth and improvement.		3.57	0.59	Strongly Agree
Supervision helps improve instructional strategies, student learning outcomes, and overall professional development.		3.63	0.53	Strongly Agree
Supervision fosters open communication, trust, and mutual respect between supervisors and teachers.		3.60	0.54	Strongly Agree
Supervisor is more towards finding teachers' weaknesses.		2.85	0.94	Agree
Supervision done is trustworthy.		3.41	0.58	Agree
The supervision is aimed at sharing shared responsibilities between teachers and supervisors		3.52	0.56	Strongly Agree
Overall		3.19	0.45	Agree
2.50-3.49	Agree/Positive	0.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree/Very Negative	

Table 1.5 shows the distribution of the respondents' attitude towards instructional supervision with an overall mean of 3.19 (SD=0.45), described as Agree and interpreted as Positive. This means that respondents perceive instructional supervision as beneficial, which is essential for fostering a supportive educational environment. It indicates that teachers see supervision as a tool for development rather than mere evaluation, they are more likely to embrace feedback and implement changes that enhance their teaching methods. This Positive attitude towards instructional supervision implies that when teachers perceive supervisors as allies, it can lead to increased sharing of best practices and mutual support and enhancing the overall educational experience. The findings underscore the importance of how instructional supervision is perceived by teachers can create avenues for teachers to provide feedback on supervisory practices, fostering an atmosphere of mutual respect and continuous improvement.

According to Elbana (2024) and Marshall (2019), teachers' attitudes toward instructional supervision can vary significantly, ranging from apprehension to appreciation, depending on the approach and execution of the supervisory process. Instructional supervision is a

process within educational settings where administrators or instructional leaders oversee and support teachers' professional development and instructional practices. It involves various activities such as classroom observations, providing constructive feedback, offering guidance on curriculum implementation, and facilitating professional development opportunities. The primary goal of instructional supervision is to enhance the quality of teaching and learning by promoting effective instructional strategies, addressing areas for improvement, and ensuring alignment with educational objectives and standards.

Notably, the indicator Supervision helps improve instructional strategies, student learning outcomes, and overall professional development received the highest mean score of 3.63 (SD = 0.53), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Very Positive. This means that respondents strongly believe in the beneficial impacts of supervision on their professional growth and the effectiveness of their teaching practices. The results imply that the instructional supervision by Master teachers is generally well-received in the Division, suggesting that it is perceived as beneficial and supportive for the majority of the teaching staff. The high levels of positive attitudes reflect that the teachers value the professional input and assistance given by the MTs as one of the significant employees of the school. This input and assistance are usually given by MTs during class observations, meetings, and in-service trainings and other related activities.

The results align with the findings of Villastique (2019), which state that supervision is viewed by teachers as a process that helps them identify and address shortcomings, leading to better teaching practices and student learning outcomes. This positive perception is particularly evident among less experienced teachers who are more open to feedback and guidance. Additionally, Elbanna (2024) asserted that teachers who have a positive attitude toward supervision often see their supervisors as knowledgeable and experienced mentors who can provide valuable insights and support. This collaborative approach fosters a sense of trust and cooperation, which is essential for effective supervision. Similarly, Berhanu (2024) explained that teachers who view supervision as a means to enhance their professional growth and development tend to have a more positive attitude towards it. This is because they see supervision as an opportunity to improve their teaching skills and stay updated on best practices in the field

On the other hand, the indicator Supervision is an examination and not a cooperation process received the highest mean score of 2.67 (SD = 0.93), described as Agree and interpreted as Positive. This means that some teachers possibly experiencing supervision as more controlling and evaluative rather than supportive. The minimal negative feedback indicates that only a small number of teachers have concerns or face challenges with the current supervision approach. It implies that if supervision is seen solely as an examination, it may hinder open communication and trust between supervisors and their supervisees that can result in a lack of feedback and support, ultimately affecting performance and morale of teachers. This could indicate a need for reforms in supervisory practices that promote collaboration among educators. Addressing these concerns through targeted support and open communication could further enhance the overall effectiveness and acceptance of instructional supervision in the division.

The study by Kurka and Berhanu (2019) claimed that teachers hold a negative attitude toward school-based instructional supervision and are dissatisfied with its implementation. Their attributed the results to supervisors who lack the necessary skills and knowledge to provide effective supervision, which negatively impacted teachers' attitudes. Hence, Basilio and Bueno (2021) posited that when instructional supervision is viewed as a collaborative and developmental effort focused on improving teaching practices and student learning outcomes, teachers are more likely to respond positively to it.

Research Question 2. What is the level of master teacher’s instructional supervisory skills based on coaching, mentoring, clinical observation, pedagogical, technological and evaluation?

Table 2.1. Distribution of Master Teachers’ Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills in Terms of Coaching

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Master teachers show commitment to their own continual learning, which is essential for guiding and supporting the professional development of other teachers	3.63	0.50	Strongly Agree
Master teachers have proven track record of high performance in teaching, including producing student gains in various settings.	3.48	0.54	Strongly Agree
They work with a diverse range of personalities among the teachers.	3.61	0.54	Strongly Agree
Master teachers are familiar with a wide range of teaching and learning styles and can support teachers with different approaches.	3.58	0.55	Strongly Agree
Master teachers understand that effective coaching is the application of adult learning theory and its application to especially to the new teachers.	3.54	0.52	Strongly Agree
Master teachers have strong interpersonal skills for sustaining a productive mentor-mentee relationship.	3.61	0.54	Strongly Agree
Master teachers have strong values, principles, and a coaching philosophy to guide teachers.	3.58	0.53	Strongly Agree
They can support teachers in navigating both successful and challenging situations.	3.62	0.52	Strongly Agree
Master teachers can demonstrate a willingness and ability to adapt and change coaching approaches based on the needs of the teachers.	3.65	0.51	Strongly Agree
Master teachers can establish a positive and supportive relationship with teachers to foster trust and collaboration.	3.70	0.48	Strongly Agree
Master teachers can provide instructional leadership by coaching colleagues, conducting observations, and facilitating professional development activities	3.63	0.55	Strongly Agree
Master teachers will empower teacher through asking powerful questions, providing constructive feedback, facilitating reflection, and encouraging action.	3.62	0.54	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.60	0.40	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend: 3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent</i>		<i>1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below Average</i>	
<i>2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average</i>		<i>1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor</i>	

Table 2.1 presents the Master Teachers’ level of instructional supervisory skills in terms of coaching, with an overall mean of 3.60 (SD = 0.40) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. This means that Master Teachers possess strong instructional supervisory skills, particularly in coaching. This suggests a high level of competence in

guiding and supporting other educators. The excellent rating of coaching skills implies that Master Teachers can serve as valuable resources for professional development within their schools and their expertise can be leveraged to train other teachers, facilitating a culture of continuous improvement. The strong agreement on coaching skills highlights the importance of ongoing professional development for educators, master teachers should continue to engage in learning opportunities to refine their skills and stay updated with the latest educational practices.

The study of Echeche (2022), in particular, focused on analyzing the coaching and mentoring performance and practices of master teachers by assessing their performance based on IPCRF ratings and their coaching and mentoring practices through a specially designed survey questionnaire encompassing eight components. The results indicated that teachers held master teachers in high regard, as evidenced by the computed negative t-values between the responses of the two groups. The correlation test revealed a significant moderate positive correlation between coaching and mentoring practices and various components. However, the performance of master teachers showed a low positive correlation with their coaching and mentoring practices in terms of interpersonal skills, and a very low positive correlation with the diversity of learners' domain.

In particular, the highest-rated indicator, with a mean of 3.70 (SD = 0.48), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent is the ability of Master Teachers can establish positive and supportive relationships with teachers, to foster trust and collaboration. The score reflects a belief that Master Teachers contribute to a positive work culture, which can lead to increased job satisfaction and morale among teachers. These results highlight the importance of strong interpersonal skills, adaptability, and a coaching philosophy rooted in adult learning theory, which empowers teachers through constructive feedback and facilitating reflection. This implies that Master Teachers can take on leadership roles in professional development, guiding their peers in building positive and supportive relationships. When master teachers make themselves accessible to teachers and being visible throughout school days and beyond in extending their help to build trust and foster open communication, it is important for them to demonstrate that they are committed to supporting teachers and are willing to work together to achieve common goals, sense of unity and shared responsibility.

Similarly, Echeche (2022) posited that strengthening the coaching relationships between teachers and the Master Teachers helps to develop a shared language that promotes effective instruction. This collaboration enhances the selection, training, and support of mentors and improves schools' effectiveness in using observation, feedback, and coaching to support the development of new and seasoned teachers.

Conversely, the lowest-rated indicator with a mean of 3.48 (SD=0.54) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent pertains to the Master teachers have proven track record of high performance in teaching, including producing student gains in various settings. This means that Master Teachers are viewed as credible and competent educators and their track record serves as validation of their expertise and effectiveness in fostering student achievement. It implies that the recognition of MT's extensive experience can lead to the establishment of professional learning communities where

educators collaborate, share experiences, and engage in reflective practice. This collaborative environment can foster continuous improvement and innovation in teaching. Networking and community engagement for Master Teachers to the wider community can fostering partnerships that enhance educational opportunities while their proven track record can attract resources, support, and collaboration from external stakeholders for a classroom environment that encourages academic success.

Hence, Abreu et al. (2019) emphasized that seeking feedback and continuous improvement is one critical aspect of improving MTs coaching skills. Regularly soliciting feedback from the teachers and even the students and using it to refine coaching strategies and improve overall effectiveness helps MTs stay adaptable and effective in their coaching roles. Master teachers have to work closely with teachers to improve their practice, focusing on content knowledge, pedagogy, and classroom management. This collaborative approach helps teachers develop their skills and confidence, leading to better student outcomes

Table 2.2. Distribution of the Master Teachers' Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills in Terms of Mentoring

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Mentor co-teachers in content and self-difficulties.	3.57	0.60	Strongly Agree
Assists in designing capacity development programs for teachers.	3.49	0.59	Strongly Agree
Conduct echo-seminars for co-teachers.	3.42	0.67	Strongly Agree
Serves as trainer in school-based INSET.	3.54	0.58	Strongly Agree
Helps in the proper and accurate dissemination or implementation of school policies.	3.60	0.56	Strongly Agree
Uses active listening skills as means to improve communication.	3.59	0.51	Strongly Agree
Conducts in-depth studies or action researches	3.22	0.84	Strongly Agree
Provide guidance and assistance as the novice teacher assumes new roles and responsibilities.	3.59	0.55	Strongly Agree
Provides a variety of growth experiences for the beginning teacher.	3.60	0.54	Strongly Agree
Assists beginning teachers in using the curriculum guide as aid for teaching.	3.68	0.51	Strongly Agree
Gives technical assistance to new teachers in formulating lesson plans.	3.64	0.60	Strongly Agree
Assists principal in instructional monitoring of teachers.	3.57	0.56	Strongly Agree
Describes the ways in which adults identify and solve problems.	3.46	0.61	Strongly Agree
Clarifies the role of observation and evaluation.	3.55	0.53	Strongly Agree
Evaluates teacher-made tests and interpret results.	3.44	0.63	Strongly Agree
Aids in applying varied teaching techniques to make teaching more fun and interactive.	3.56	0.63	Strongly Agree
Facilitates in conceptualizing training proposals during INSET.	3.51	0.60	Strongly Agree
Contributes ideas in crafting the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP).	3.45	0.70	Strongly Agree
Assist the school head in instructional monitoring of teachers.	3.60	0.59	Strongly Agree
Assists school head in class monitoring.	3.57	0.60	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.53	0.44	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent</i>	<i>1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below Average</i>	
	<i>2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average</i>	<i>1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor</i>	

Table 2.2 shows the distribution of the Master Teachers' level of instructional supervisory skills in terms of mentoring with an overall mean score of 3.53 (SD=0.44) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. The excellent rating of mentoring skills

means that Master Teachers are committed to their own professional development and to helping other teachers grow. They likely engage in ongoing learning to refine their mentoring strategies and stay updated with the latest educational practices. This implies that the strong mentoring skills are well-positioned to take on formal mentorship roles in guiding novice teachers or those who are seeking assistance to enhance their instructional practices that can help build a supportive teaching community and facilitate the transfer of knowledge and experience. The high level of mentoring skills among Master Teachers suggests a collaborative culture within the educational environment, the culture that encourages peer-to-peer learning and the sharing of best practices. Master Teachers may employ different mentoring approaches based on the needs and learning styles of their mentees to ensure that mentoring is tailored to individual needs while maximizing its effectiveness.

According to Buagas and Ching (2023) posited that mentoring as an aspect of instructional supervision aims to enhance learning outcomes and elevate the quality of education by enhancing students' cognitive achievements. Mentoring is geared towards equipping teachers with comprehensive competencies, including personal, pedagogical, professional, and social skills. Through mentoring, school principals and master teachers support teachers in managing the learning process and enhancing their professionalism, particularly in the preparation of learning materials. Hence, instructional supervision should prioritize the development of all aspects of teacher competence (Sartana, 2020).

The highest-rated indicator with mean scores of 3.68 (SD=3.64), described as Strongly Agree, and interpreted as Excellent was Assisst beginning teachers in using the curriculum guide as aide for teaching. The result means that Master Teachers are perceived as highly effective in supporting beginning teachers and play a crucial role in helping novice educators navigate the curriculum and utilize it effectively in their teaching practices, respectively. The implication is that providing strong support through effective mentoring can lead to higher retention rates among beginning teachers since new educators can feel that they are supported and equipped to succeed, they are more likely to strengthen their commitment as educators. The division implements structured mentorship programs where Master Teachers are assigned as mentors to new teachers. These programs include regular meetings, observations, and feedback sessions to support the professional growth of new educators.

The results which reflect the MTs efficiency in mentoring new teachers corroborate the claim of Dingal (2023) and Ikromova (2020) that the mentoring of master teachers consistently provides opportunities, especially for new teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in developing teaching materials and employing various learning methods. These skills positively impact both teachers' performance and students' academic achievement (Sangalang, 2018). Similarly, Felisilda and Malaga (2019) found that mentoring practice helps teachers as they are provided with guidance that makes teaching and learning more manageable. It also involves sharing of experiences, provision of feedback, and offering of practical advice to navigate challenges and capitalize on opportunities.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicator, with a mean score of 3.22 (SD = 0.84), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent pertains to Conducts in-depth studies or action research. This means that Master Teachers excel in direct mentorship and instructional support, but there is potential for growth in their involvement with research activities. Enhancing their skills in this area could make their mentorship even more effective as they could incorporate evidence-based practices and continuous improvement techniques into their mentoring strategies. The conduct in-depth studies imply that enhancement of mentoring skills can address specific classroom challenges, and implement strategies that are proven to be effective, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education. They are encouraged to look into specific problems or challenges in their classrooms, create innovations, and document the process through an action research so that their actions and innovations are supported with evidences. It suggests that the school or Division may conduct an annual division-wide research congress for educators to share their findings, collaborate, and further improve teaching practices across the board. Yet, many teachers and MTs are grappling with the challenges of conducting research, hence, it is an area that really needs improvement.

Basilio and Bueno (2021) posited that despite being a challenging task, conducting research can be a highly motivating and energizing experience for master teachers, as it allows them to explore new ideas, evaluate teaching practices, and re-evaluate daily choices based on evidence and guiding questions. Echeche (2022) emphasized that Master teachers can improve their mentoring of other teachers by adopting a more structured and supportive approach. This involves setting clear goals and expectations, providing regular feedback and guidance, and fostering a collaborative learning environment. Additionally, they can facilitate peer-to-peer learning by organizing workshops, coaching sessions, and professional development opportunities that allow teachers to share their expertise and learn from one another.

Table 2.3 Distribution of the Master Teachers' Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills in Terms of Clinical Observation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Approach teachers with empathy, creating a safe environment for open communication.	3.72	0.45	Strongly Agree
Actively listen, provide constructive feedback, and articulate expectations clearly.	3.70	0.50	Strongly Agree
Engage in reflective practice enhances self-awareness and critical thinking.	3.68	0.49	Strongly Agree
Adapt supervision to individual learning styles and needs is crucial for effective guidance	3.61	0.54	Strongly Agree
Stay updated with the latest research, techniques, and ethical guidelines to inspire teachers to grow professionally.	3.44	0.63	Strongly Agree
Balance constructive feedback with praise motivates supervisees to excel and improve continuously.	3.62	0.54	Strongly Agree
Understand the role of clinical supervision in monitoring and ensuring quality services.	3.66	0.49	Strongly Agree
Familiarize with various theoretical models of clinical supervision and establish a productive learning.	3.46	0.60	Strongly Agree
Adherence to professional and ethical standards, such as protecting and maintaining confidentiality.	3.63	0.48	Strongly Agree
Create a respectful environment, seek.	3.71	0.46	Strongly Agree

Overall	3.62	0.40	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend: 3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent</i>	<i>1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below Average</i>		
<i>2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average</i>	<i>1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor</i>		

Table 2.3 presents the Master Teachers' level of instructional supervisory skills in terms of clinical observation, including ten indicators assessed with the overall mean score of 3.62 (SD=0.40), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. The strong agreement on their skills in clinical observation means that the supervisory role that Master Teachers is important in guiding and mentoring other educators which reinforces their status as instructional leaders in school. Their proficiency in clinical observation implies that Master Teachers can lead professional development sessions focused on observation techniques and feedback strategies that can help other educators refine their teaching practices and enhance their own observational skills. It suggests that MT's may employ differentiated supervisory skills and observation techniques address the specific needs of the teachers they are observing to ensures relevant and actionable feedback and maximizing its impact on teaching practices.

According to Marciano et al. (2019) by observing teachers in action, Master Teachers can also model effective instructional techniques, foster reflective practice, and promote a culture of continuous improvement within the educational community

Among the indicators, the highest-rated aspect is on Approach teachers with empathy, creating a safe environment for open communication with a mean of 3.72 (SD=0.45), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. Approaching teachers with empathy means fostering a supportive educational environment through recognizing the importance of emotional intelligence in educational leadership and building rapport with teachers to foster open communication, and promote a positive and supportive atmosphere conducive to professional growth and development. This implies that schools can invest in training programs that focus specifically on developing empathy and communication skills among teachers such as workshops and seminars that can provide educators with practical strategies for fostering empathetic interactions. The emphasis on empathy can significantly influence the overall school culture that is likely to promote collaboration, reduce conflicts, and create a more positive work environment, which can enhance teacher retention.

According to Barrogo (2020) classroom observation using the standardized tools is made a requirement in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS), enhancing its objectivity and standardization. Its multifaceted use in mentoring, coaching, performance review, and evaluation contributes to teachers' continuous professional growth. In line with this, Suparto (2020) highlighted that academic supervision utilizing clinical observation technique can enhance the quality of teacher learning.

Conversely, the lowest-rated indicator Stay updated with the latest research, techniques, and ethical guidelines to inspire teachers to grow professionally with a mean of 3.44 (SD=0.63) described as Strongly Agree interpreted as Excellent. This means that educators who prioritize staying informed in the recent researches can serve as role

models for their peers by demonstrating a commitment to professional growth and ethical standards, they can inspire other teachers to engage in similar practices. It implies that emphasizing the importance of staying updated can encourage teachers to engage in reflective practices, teachers should be prompted to assess how new information and ethical guidelines can be integrated into their teaching methods. The insights emphasize the importance of a lifelong learning mindset, ethical considerations, and collaboration in fostering a thriving educational environment to grow professionally that ultimately beneficial to both educators and students. It also points to the necessity of creating a more solid and appropriate system for professional growth that encourages and facilitates the ongoing acquisition of new knowledge and skills.

Felisilda and Malaga (2019) posited that engaging with current research enables master teachers to make informed, evidence-based decisions about curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment. This helps ensure that teaching practices are grounded in the latest findings and feedback during clinical observations are precisely aligned with proven educational strategies. Consequently, feedback during clinical observations becomes more constructive and targeted, allowing teachers to implement effective practices that have been validated through research. Meanwhile, Guanzon and Miranda (2023) explained that regularly reviewing academic journals of different researches, research databases, and other literature can help master teachers stay informed about cutting-edge research, techniques, and ethical considerations. This proactive approach ensures that they are well-equipped to integrate new methodologies and insights into their teaching practices.

Table 2.4. Distribution of the Master Teachers' Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills in Terms of Pedagogical Dimension

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Teaches accurate and updated content using appropriate approaches and strategies.	3.61	0.53	Strongly Agree
Aligns lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional strategies.	3.75	0.46	Strongly Agree
Encourages learners to use higher order thinking skills in asking questions.	3.77	0.44	Strongly Agree
Engages and sustains learners' interest in the subject matter by making content meaningful and relevant.	3.74	0.50	Strongly Agree
Establishes routines and procedures to maximize use of time, instructional materials.	3.67	0.53	Strongly Agree
Integrates language, literacy, skills and values in teaching.	3.71	0.48	Strongly Agree
Presents lesson logically in development manner.	3.72	0.45	Strongly Agree
Utilizes technology resources in planning, designing and delivery of the lesson.	3.68	0.47	Strongly Agree
Creates situations that encourage learners to use higher order thinking skills.	3.70	0.46	Strongly Agree
Sets lesson objectives within the experiences and capabilities of the learners.	3.72	0.47	Strongly Agree
Utilizes varied techniques and strategies suited to different kinds of learners.	3.71	0.45	Strongly Agree
Shows fairness in dealing with the learners.	3.76	0.43	Strongly Agree
Paces lesson appropriate to the needs and difficulties	3.70	0.52	Strongly Agree
Provides appropriate intervention activities for learners at risk.	3.69	0.52	Strongly Agree
Helps learners answer in own words at a desired cognitive level.	3.71	0.48	Strongly Agree
Facilitates students in asking questions relevant to the lesson.	3.73	0.44	Strongly Agree
Facilitates students in participating actively in the learning tasks with some levels of independence.	3.73	0.48	Strongly Agree
Guides students in showing appropriate behavior of individualism, cooperation competition in classroom interaction.	3.70	0.52	Strongly Agree

Helps students in imbibing the valuing learning from the teacher & classmates.	3.72	0.47	Strongly Agree
Invites students in demonstrating varied ways, learning achieved in the activities.	3.69	0.48	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.71	0.36	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent</i>	<i>1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below Average</i>	
	<i>2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average</i>	<i>1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor</i>	

Table 2.4 highlights the result of the Master Teachers' level of instructional supervisory skills in terms of pedagogical dimension with an overall mean score of 3.71 (SD=0.36,) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. This means that Master Teachers are instructional leaders who possess the knowledge and skills necessary to guide and support other educators in improving their pedagogical practices and enhancing student learning outcomes. This implies that excellent pedagogical skills play a significant role in curriculum development to ensure that curricula are aligned with best practices, responsive to student needs, and promote active learning. The high level of pedagogical competencies among Master Teachers suggests a commitment to continuous professional growth especially when engaged in ongoing learning to refine their skills and stay updated with the latest research and best practices in education.

The study of Mendoza and Bautista (2023) revealed the significant relationship between master teachers' pedagogical practices and the instructional competence and performance of teachers.

Among the indicators, the highest score is observed in the indicator, encourages learners to use higher order thinking skills in asking questions with a mean score of 3.77 (SD=0.44) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. This means that master teachers excel in fostering critical thinking among students, which is crucial for their cognitive development and deeper understanding of the subject matter. The implication of this high score is that these educators are effectively cultivating a classroom environment that stimulates intellectual curiosity and promotes active engagement in learning. It suggests that Master Teachers can facilitate and encourage other teachers to use inquiry-based activities and investigations where students explore topics, pose questions, conduct research, and draw conclusions. Enhancing curiosity, independent thinking, and exploration, fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and investigative skills.

The results aligned with the findings of Mendoza and Bautista (2023) that all teachers must infuse their lessons with real-world examples and applications, making the subject matter more relatable and engaging. This helps students connect abstract concepts to practical situations, fostering critical thinking.

Marciano et al. (2019) emphasized that master teachers exhibit and can illustrate pedagogical expertise by bridging theoretical concepts with practical application and exemplifying effective teaching methods. They serve as dynamic models of proficient teaching, fostering and prompting self-reflection among educators since they view learning as a mutual exchange and approach their interactions with teachers as collaborative partnerships. Therefore, mentoring not only facilitates the professional development of teachers but also enhances teaching methodologies. Moreover, it positively impacts students' academic achievements.

Conversely, the lowest score is indicator Teaches accurate and updated content using appropriate approaches and strategies, with a mean score of 3.61 (SD=0.53) described as Strongly Agree and described as Excellent. This means that while still within the realm of excellence, this indicator highlights an area where there may be some room for improvement, teachers are effectively aligning their instruction with curriculum standards and learning objectives that ensures the content taught is relevant and meets educational requirements, which in turn enhances the educational experience for students. The implication here could be that while the master teachers are proficient in structuring learning activities and facilitating academic growth, they still feel the need to access more opportunities that could help them enhance their guidance in promoting positive social interactions and behaviors among students. This is crucial as it would be difficult for them to aid newly-hired teachers on teaching pedagogy if they themselves are not updated and knowledgeable of the recent teaching strategies and methodologies. Strategies such as fostering a culture of collaboration, emphasizing empathy and respect, and providing clear expectations for behavior could also be beneficial in addressing this aspect of instructional supervision.

Abreu et al. (2019) expounded that schools can help Master teachers stay updated on the recent content and strategies of teaching by providing them with opportunities for continuous professional development. This can include seminars and trainings that focus on the latest developments in their subject area, as well as encouraging them to engage in professional activities that enhance their instructional competence and develop leadership capacity. Matias (2023) believed that Master teachers can also be encouraged to design training programs for their colleagues, which could provide technical assistance and enhance the overall teaching competence of the school workforce. Master teachers initiate activities that can enhance teacher’s performance and productive student outcomes.

Table 2.5. Distribution of the Master Teachers’ Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills in Terms of Technological

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Use various observation systems to analyze and understand the instructional process within a classroom setting.	3.47	0.52	Strongly Agree
Evaluate the effectiveness of instructional design and modifying technical training instruction accordingly.	3.62	0.62	Strongly Agree
Review, interpret and implement instructional materials to meet training readiness standards.	3.49	0.55	Strongly Agree
Incorporate technology into educational practices to enhance learning outcomes and support instructional programs effectively.	3.65	0.51	Strongly Agree
Competent in creating and delivering electronic presentations for teaching purposes.	3.46	0.58	Strongly Agree
Efficiently navigate the internet for educational resources and information using advanced search techniques.	3.50	0.52	Strongly Agree
Has skill in sending, receiving, and managing email communications effectively with colleagues and students.	3.54	0.60	Strongly Agree
Incorporate technology effectively into teaching practices to engage students in learning.	3.52	0.51	Strongly Agree
Uses data to inform teaching decisions, target areas for improvement, and track student progress over time.	3.58	0.51	Strongly Agree

Develop critical thinking, collaboration, communication, and creativity skills in students through technology use.	3.59	0.51	Strongly Agree
Engage students in technology tools like video, email, online programs, and video conferencing.	3.57	0.58	Strongly Agree
Updated with technological advancements in education and striving for excellence in technology skills.	3.52	0.61	Strongly Agree
Continuously improve technology skills through training, workshops, and networking opportunities within the educational community.	3.60	0.53	Strongly Agree
Efficiently navigate the web for educational resources and materials to enhance teaching practices.	3.53	0.57	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.54	0.41	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend:</i>			
	<i>3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent</i>	<i>1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below Average</i>	
	<i>2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average</i>	<i>1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor</i>	

Table 2.5 shows the master teachers' instructional supervisory skills in terms of technology with an overall mean score of 3.54 (SD=0.41), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. This means that Master Teachers demonstrate a high level of proficiency in utilizing technology to support and enhance educational practices, reflecting their readiness to integrate modern technological tools into the classroom effectively. Given the strong technological skills, implies that integrating technology into the curriculum plays significant role to support learning objectives, promote active engagement, and develop digital literacy skills among students. Sharing of best practices and educational technology resources, teachers can collectively enhance their instructional effectiveness. Master Teachers may utilize educational technology to collect and analyze student performance data as baseline in choosing appropriate instructional strategies, identify areas for improvement, and personalize learning experiences for students.

In line with the study of Javier (2020) that the Department of Education can assist Master Teachers in enhancing their technological skills by providing them with professional development opportunities and resources. One such initiative is the Higher Order Thinking Skills Professional Learning Packages (HOTS-PLPs) program, which aims to support Master Teachers in mentoring their colleagues to improve their pedagogy and assessment practices. This program includes guide materials and technical assistance to help Master Teachers in their roles, focusing on integrating HOTS into classroom practices (Gita-Carlos, 2024). Additionally, the Department can offer training sessions and workshops on emerging technologies, such as online learning platforms and educational software.

Among the various indicators, the result indicates that the highest mean of 3.65 (SD=0.51) is on the indicator, incorporate technology into educational practices to enhance learning outcomes and support educational programs effectively, which is described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. This means that Master teachers are particularly proficient in assessing the quality and impact of their instructional methods and are adept at adjusting technical assistance to improve outcomes. This high proficiency implies that these teachers possess strong technological skills, enabling them to critically analyze instructional design, identify areas for improvement, and implement necessary modifications effectively. The results reflect that the Master Teachers in the locale of study

are competent in their roles of evaluating instructional design and that they could also provide suggestions and recommendations to their fellow teachers on how to improve instructional designs for a positive learning outcome in the classroom. This capability is essential for fostering an adaptive and responsive teaching environment, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education and ensuring that instructional strategies meet the evolving needs of students.

The results on the master teachers' technological skills align with the explanation of Barruga (2021) that Master teachers, just like other teachers, also require technological skills to fulfill key responsibilities like crafting self-learning modules, coaching on learning activity sheets, planning module distribution and retrieval, and preparing for classroom observations. Proficiency with online tools and platforms is essential for master teachers to provide technical assistance to teachers on new strategies and schemes for teaching and learning.

Conversely, the lowest mean score was recorded for the indicator, Competent in creating and delivering electronic presentations for teaching purposes, which has a mean of 3.46 (SD=0.58), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. This slightly lower score means that the Master teachers need more training and assistance in technological proficiency when it comes to creating and delivering online presentations. This could imply that there is a varying degree of technological skills among the respondents as indicated by the high standard deviation. Those who are less comfortable with basic technology may struggle more with advanced tasks like creating engaging electronic presentations. Additionally, the MTs may not have received adequate training focused specifically on creating and delivering electronic presentations. While general technology training might be available, specialized workshops or courses on presentation skills might be lacking. Trainings and seminars on the use of technology in the classroom can be conducted regularly for all teachers to be equipped with the necessary technological skills.

The results aligned with the findings of Bañares and Pimentel (2021), who revealed that master teachers commonly face challenges such as insufficient knowledge and skills, technical difficulties, and staying abreast of technological advancements in education. A majority of these master teachers express feelings of being ill-equipped to guide others in utilizing technology positively.

Table 2.6. Distribution of the Master Teachers' Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills in Terms of Evaluation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Evaluate students' performances fairly and uses adequate and accurate standards measures of evaluation	3.70	0.46	Strongly Agree
Selects and utilizes criterion referenced tests.	3.51	0.52	Strongly Agree
Analyzes and interprets evaluation results skillfully.	3.56	0.50	Strongly Agree
Utilizes evaluation result as a basis for improving instruction.	3.63	0.49	Strongly Agree
Uses varied forms of evaluation tools.	3.59	0.53	Strongly Agree

Evaluates performance of the students on the basis of the course objectives through discussions, quizzes, and major examinations.	3.69	0.47	Strongly Agree
Gives grades on the basis of students' performance.	3.78	0.42	Strongly Agree
Treats each student fair and square.	3.77	0.42	Strongly Agree
Exercises no favoritism.	3.71	0.51	Strongly Agree
Acts according to own intellectual judgment.	3.55	0.55	Strongly Agree
Acts according to own intellectual judgment.	3.57	0.58	Strongly Agree
Provides evaluative activities appropriate to students' abilities, interest, and needs.	3.92	0.83	Strongly Agree
Gives evaluation result ratings that are well-accepted by the students.	3.66	0.49	Strongly Agree
Utilizes evaluation result as a basis for improving instruction.	3.66	0.55	Strongly Agree
Uses different methods in evaluating students' learning aligned to the learning objectives such as oral performance, projects and hands-on	4.01	0.75	Strongly Agree
Includes items in the tests that are based on lesson objectives consisted with actual discussions activities and classroom interactions.	3.69	0.52	Strongly Agree
Gives grades on the basis of students' actual performance.	3.75	0.46	Strongly Agree
Treats each student fairly in giving grades.	3.75	0.46	Strongly Agree
Bases ratings according to the objectives of the lessons & criteria set in class.	3.69	0.48	Strongly Agree
Allows students to rate their own performances in some of the activities in the class.	3.56	0.57	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.69	0.42	Strongly agree
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent</i>	<i>1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below Average</i>	
	<i>2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average</i>	<i>1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor</i>	

Table 2.6 shows the statistical result of the master teachers' level of instructional supervisory skills in terms of evaluation, as evidenced by an overall mean score of 3.69 (SD=0.42), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent. Denoting excellence in the indicators mentioned means robust competency among master teachers in assessing student performance and utilizing evaluation results to enhance instruction. The consistently high ratings indicate their adeptness in employing fair and accurate evaluation measures, utilizing diverse evaluation tools, and aligning evaluation methods with learning objectives. Proficiency in evaluation can foster collaboration among educators by sharing best practices and insights gained from evaluations, they can help create a supportive professional learning community that enhances instructional effectiveness.

According to Sangalang (2018), master teachers, regarded as highly proficient instructional leaders, employ various methods to support their skills and duties by aiding teachers in orchestrating student learning through well-structured lesson plans and utilizing suitable, comprehensive, and up-to-date instructional assessment and evaluation materials

In particular, the highest-rated indicator has a mean of 4.01 (SD=0.75) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent is about the abilities of master teachers to Use different methods in evaluating students' learning aligned to the learning objectives such as oral performance, projects, hands-on. This means a deep understanding of student diversity and a commitment to fostering equitable learning environments. The consistency among teachers in addressing student differences reflects positively on

instructional quality and promotes student engagement and motivation. In the context of the Department of Education, it implies that all the teachers are encouraged to use different forms of assessment, such as diagnostic, formative, standardized, and summative, to evaluate the learners' knowledge and skills. These competencies inform teachers on how they could contextualize their lessons and strategies to best fit the learners' learning style for the achievement of the education outcomes. Through evaluation, master teachers assess the effectiveness of instructional methods, curriculum materials, and learning strategies, ensuring alignment with educational goals and standards. They meticulously analyze student performance data to identify strengths and areas needing improvement, enabling targeted interventions to support diverse learning needs.

According to Sangalang (2018), master teachers, regarded as highly proficient instructional leaders, employ various methods to support their skills and duties by aiding teachers in orchestrating student learning through well-structured lesson plans and utilizing suitable, comprehensive, and up-to-date instructional assessment and evaluation materials. Similarly, Echeche (2022) advocated that effective teaching emerges when teams of master teachers engage in a cyclical process. This process involves analyzing data, establishing learning objectives for both students and educators derived from this analysis, collaborating to develop lessons incorporating evidence-based strategies, and evaluating the impact of their learning and teamwork on student achievement.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean, 3.51 (SD=0.52), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Excellent was about the master teachers' skills in Select and utilizes criterion referenced tests. This means that MT's are perceived to have a strong ability to select and effectively utilize criterion-referenced tests in assessing student performance against specific criteria rather than comparing students to one another. The strong skills in utilizing criterion-referenced tests imply that Master Teachers can help align assessments with curriculum objectives. This ensures that assessments accurately measure student learning outcomes and inform instructional practices. This gap underlines the importance of ensuring assessments accurately measure student mastery of learning objectives and inform instructional decision-making.

Matias (2023) claimed that addressing the proficiency gap on designing criterion-referenced assessments can be done through strategic resource allocation, quality assurance measures, and a culture of continuous improvement that will not only strengthen assessment practices but also contribute to the overall quality and effectiveness of education within Department of Education.

Table 2.7. Summary of Master Teachers Level of Instructional Supervisory Skills

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Coaching	3.60	0.40	Excellent
Mentoring	3.53	0.44	Excellent
Clinical Observation	3.62	0.40	Excellent
Pedagogical	3.71	0.36	Excellent
Technological	3.54	0.41	Excellent

Evaluation	3.69	0.42	Excellent
Overall	3.62	0.41	Excellent
Legend	3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Excellent 2.61 – 3.40 Agree/Average	1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/Below average 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Poor	

Table 2.7 reflects the summary of Master Teachers level of instructional supervisory skills across six different components- coaching, mentoring, clinical observation, pedagogical, technological, and evaluation which reflects consistently high ratings across all components, with an overall mean score of 3.62 (SD = 0.41), indicating an overall Excellent performance and interpreted as Strongly Agree. The results mean that master teachers demonstrate proficiency in coaching, mentoring, clinical observation, pedagogical knowledge, technological integration, and evaluation. The consistently high ratings suggest that the master teachers possess strong instructional leadership skills, which are crucial for guiding and supporting other teachers in improving their teaching practices. The high ratings underscore the effectiveness of master teachers in providing support and guidance to their peers in various aspects of teaching and learning, which highlights the importance of ongoing training and mentorship programs that have contributed to the development of these supervisory skills. Moreover, excellent performance in evaluation indicates a strong system of assessing teaching practices and student outcomes, which is essential for continuous improvement and quality assurance in education.

The results strengthen the position of Buagas and Ching (2023) that Master teachers play a vital role in schools by fostering a culture of lifelong learning and intellectual growth. They are leaders who set a positive example, encouraging students to take up the challenges of learning and teaching. These educators go beyond simply imparting knowledge, focusing on the intellectual, emotional, and physical development of their students.

Additionally, Ordanel and Dioso (2023) emphasized that the instructional supervisory skills of Master Teachers are crucial for effective teaching and learning in schools. Their expertise in instructional supervision also helps to foster a positive learning environment, accommodate diverse learners, and promote continuous professional growth among teachers. Moreover, Master Teachers' ability to engage in professional learning communities and discuss concerns related to their duties and responsibilities enhances their competence as instructional leaders.

Hence, Cortez (2023) asserted that the Master Teachers' should be given extra assistance in their instructional supervision by providing necessary resources and support. One key strategy is to ensure that master teachers are equipped with the latest pedagogical knowledge and technological skills, which are crucial for effective instructional supervision. This can be achieved through regular training and professional development opportunities that focus on integrating technology into teaching and learning processes.

Research Question 3. What is the level of teachers' performance with regard to teaching and learning process, student's outcome, community involvement, professional growth and development?

Table 3.1. Distribution of the Teachers' Level of Performance in Terms of Teaching and Learning Process

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Chooses activities relevant to the prescribed curriculum	3.65	0.48	Strongly Agree
Plans student grouping according to instructional needs	3.63	0.49	Strongly Agree
Informs students of objective of the lesson	3.60	0.52	Strongly Agree
Relates the lesson to previous and future lessons	3.69	0.47	Strongly Agree
Monitors student learning continuously	3.66	0.50	Strongly Agree
Provides feedback and re-teaches when necessary	3.60	0.52	Strongly Agree
Provides opportunities for students to practice independently	3.65	0.50	Strongly Agree
Establishes a level of difficulty which encourages success	3.54	0.53	Strongly Agree
Demonstrates enthusiasm, vigor, involvement, and interest in lesson presentation	3.65	0.49	Strongly Agree
Presents learning content in a logical sequential order	3.58	0.52	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.63	0.38	Strongly Agree
Legend:	3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Outstanding	1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ Satisfactory	
	2.61 – 3.40 Agree / Very Satisfactory	1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/ Poor	

Table 3.1 shows the statistical results of the teachers' level of performance in terms of teaching and learning process with an overall mean score of 3.63 (SD=0.38), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This high mean means that teachers are consistently demonstrating proficiency in their instructional practices, creating an environment conducive to student engagement, learning, and growth. This reflects their ability to effectively facilitate the teaching and learning process, engage students, and achieve educational objectives. The emphasis on outstanding performance implies that teaching practices should continue to prioritize student-centered learning which includes engaging students through active learning strategies, differentiated instruction, and formative assessments that cater to diverse learning styles. It could be suggested that teachers need to be adaptable and responsive to the needs of their students. This flexibility is essential in addressing diverse learning needs and creating an inclusive classroom environment.

Pandolpho (2019) explained that the primary goal of schools is to design a teacher evaluation system that evaluates subtle aspects, implements adjustments as needed, and enhances the teacher's effectiveness. This is because the greater a teacher's effectiveness, the more successful their students are likely to be (Balanquit et al., 2023).

Among the indicator, Relates the lesson to previous and future lessons stands out with the highest mean score of 3.69 (SD = 0.47), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This means that teachers excel in establishing connections between current lesson content and past or future learning experiences, promoting coherence and continuity in students' understanding. Such integration of concepts across lessons not only enhances comprehension but also fosters a deeper understanding of the subject

matter and its relevance to broader contexts. Examples of classroom activities and strategies that teachers use to ensure that they relate their lessons to previous and future lessons are the use of review and preview sessions, concept mapping or mind mapping, journal writing, among others. These practices not only help students make connections between past, present, and future learning but also reinforce their understanding and retention of the material.

The results strengthen the claim of Pandolpho (2019) that designing lessons that show the connection between topics is crucial for helping students understand the relevance and significance of what they are learning. When lessons are structured to explicitly engage students' prior knowledge and actively explore new concepts through authentic inquiry, it can facilitate deeper learning and integration of new information.

Munna and Kalam (2021) advised that building connections between lessons can be done by identifying the desired learning outcomes and then planning the lesson activities to achieve those goals. This helps ensure the lesson is focused and coherent.

Meanwhile, the indicator Establishes a level of difficulty which encourages success presents the lowest mean score of 3.54 (SD=0.53, described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding). This means that students may not be experiencing optimal growth in their learning without appropriately challenging tasks. Students miss out on opportunities to stretch their abilities and develop resilience in the face of difficult problems. This lack of challenge can lead to complacency, where students are not pushed to apply critical thinking or develop problem-solving skills, ultimately affecting their long-term academic performance and preparedness for future educational endeavors. suggests that most of the teachers do not create lessons and exams in a difficult manner. While teachers demonstrate overall effectiveness in designing instructional tasks, they think that they still do not establish enough level of difficulty that encourages success for the students. Thus, even though teachers are effective overall, adjusting the level of difficulty in their instructional design is essential to better support and encourage student success. This points to a potential need for more effective instructional differentiation, where teachers can better tailor the level of challenge to match the diverse abilities and learning needs of their students.

Tiplin (2022) expounded that making challenging or higher-order lessons is crucial for students' cognitive development and academic success. These skills are essential for preparing students to tackle complex problems, think creatively, and make informed decisions in their personal and professional lives. By incorporating higher-order thinking into lessons, teachers can move students beyond mere memorization and encourage them to develop deeper understanding and connections between concepts.

Table 3.2. Distribution of the Teachers' Level of Performance in Terms of Student's Outcome

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Communicates expectations of performance to students	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
Uses objective student data to set expectations	3.52	0.53	Strongly Agree
Uses evaluative feedback to determine level of skill acquisition	3.57	0.51	Strongly Agree
Encourages participation from all students	3.72	0.45	Strongly Agree
Use higher order questioning techniques to promote critical thinking skills	3.63	0.51	Strongly Agree
Provides opportunities for each student to meet success regularly	3.64	0.49	Strongly Agree
Creates a climate in which students display initiative and assume a personal responsibility for learning	3.61	0.51	Strongly Agree
Manages disruptive behavior constructively	3.53	0.53	Strongly Agree
Establishes and clearly communicates parameters for student classroom behavior	3.60	0.50	Strongly Agree
Makes opportunities for one-to-one conferences to discuss student progress	3.56	0.52	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.60	0.39	Strongly Agree
Legend:	3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Outstanding	1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ Satisfactory	
	2.61 – 3.40 Agree / Very Satisfactory	1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/ Poor	

Table 3.2 reflects the statistical results of teachers' level of performance based on student outcomes with an overall mean score of 3.60 (SD=0.39), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This overall score means a high level of effectiveness among teachers in nurturing positive student outcomes across various performance indicators. Such a score implies that the majority of respondents agree on the effectiveness of teaching practices and their positive impact on learning outcomes. This highlights the need for continued investment in teacher development, comprehensive evaluation methods, and a focus on creating engaging learning environments. By understanding the factors that contribute to effective teaching can enhance student outcomes and prepare them to the 21st-century learning skills.

The results corroborate the findings of Batuguis et al. (2022) that the methods and resources employed by teachers are vital components of effective teaching practices that directly influence student outcomes. Utilizing diverse instructional strategies, such as active learning techniques, differentiated instruction, and technology integration, can help teachers cater to the diverse needs and learning styles of their students.

Among the ten evaluated indicators, the highest mean score is observed in the statement, encourages participation from all students, which has a mean of 3.72 (SD=0.45), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This means that teachers are particularly effective in engaging students and promoting inclusive participation in the classroom. The high mean score in this area underscores the importance of active student involvement as a critical component of effective teaching practices, as it can lead to better student engagement, motivation, and overall academic achievement. The teachers really encourage open-ended discussions where students are invited to question, debate, and discuss various topics that can promote active participation. Socratic

seminars, in particular, involve students in a structured dialogue based on a text or topic, fostering deep thinking and broad participation.

According to Andriani and Rasto (2019), learning outcomes represent the achievement of students in meeting the established learning objectives. These outcomes are considered successful when students have attained the learning goals and demonstrate changes in knowledge, attitudes, and skills. Moreover, Pido et al. (2023) emphasized that when teachers perform well, they are better equipped to create a dynamic and efficient teaching and learning process, which in turn enhances student learning outcomes. Effective teacher performance can lead to improved student understanding, retention, and application of knowledge, as well as positive changes in attitudes and skills.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean score is the indicator Uses objective student data to set expectations, with a mean of 3.52 (SD = 0.53) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This means that there are instances where teachers do not extensively rely on measurable and objective data about students' academic performance to guide their teaching strategies, set learning goals, or assess progress. Instead, they might use subjective judgments, impressions, or general observations. The implication here is that while teachers are adept in most areas, there is room for improvement in the use of data-driven decision-making to tailor and set realistic and challenging expectations for students.

In terms of using objective data, Sarabia and Collantes (2020) emphasized that objective assessments provide quick and accurate feedback on student performance, helping them identify areas where they need to focus their study efforts.

Table 3.3. Distribution of the Teachers' Level of Performance in Terms of Community Involvement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Encourages community involvement with the school	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
Provides a climate which opens up communication between the teacher and parent	3.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
Communicates with parents in the best interest of the students	3.63	0.48	Strongly Agree
Supports parents/teacher activities	3.56	0.50	Strongly Agree
Provides information related to support resources	3.58	0.50	Strongly Agree
Cooperates with other teachers, the administration, and other educational personnel	3.62	0.50	Strongly Agree
Shares ideas and methods with other teachers	3.58	0.50	Strongly Agree
Informs administration and/or appropriate personnel of school related items	3.53	0.52	Strongly Agree
Makes use of support services as needed	3.55	0.52	Strongly Agree
Participates in community and stakeholder's engagement activities	3.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.58	0.37	Strongly Agree
Legend:	3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Outstanding	1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ Satisfactory	
	2.61 – 3.40 Agree / Very Satisfactory	1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/ Poor	

Table 3.3 shows the statistical results of the teachers' level performance in terms of community involvement, with an overall mean score of 3.58 (SD=0.37), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This outstanding performance means a commitment to building partnerships that enhance educational experiences and outcomes for students by recognizing the significance of community involvement, educational stakeholders can prioritize strategies that support teachers in their efforts. It implies that community involvement is not just an ancillary aspect of teaching; it is a vital component that enriches the educational landscape and contributes to the holistic development of students. By continuing to invest in community engagement initiatives, schools can create a more supportive and effective educational environment. Teachers who engage with the community help build social capital, which can enhance trust, cooperation, and collective efficacy among community members. It further suggests that by advocating for educational issues and engaging in community service, teachers can become role models for students and inspire civic responsibility. Community involvement encourages collaborative learning environments where students, teachers, and community members work together toward common goals. This collaboration can lead to innovative educational practices and programs that address needs and challenges in educational environment.

The results align with the explanation of Daly (2022) that teachers are crucial in developing and maintaining effective school-community relations. They serve as liaisons, interpreting the school's program to the community and clarifying the school's role in society.

Among the ten evaluated indicators, the highest mean score is observed in Communicates with parents in the best interest of the students, which scored 3.63 (SD=0.48), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This indicator highlights the significance of effective communication between teachers and parents in fostering student success. By maintaining open and proactive dialogue focused on the welfare and academic progress of students, teachers can cultivate a supportive partnership with parents, which is crucial for student achievement. The constant communication with parents is practiced by the teachers by conducting regular PTA meetings, family day, and other school activities that encourage the parents to take an active participation as they are also the time that the parents can consult the teachers about the progress of their children. Additionally, the teachers see to it that the parents sign the test papers of their children after exams so they are aware of the scores. This is one way of indirectly informing the parents how their students are faring in their education.

Additionally, Francisco (2019) asserted that teachers who are involved in the community gain a deeper understanding of their students' needs and can tailor their teaching methods accordingly. This direct relationship with parents also helps teachers identify areas where students may need additional support.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.53 (SD=0.52) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding is the indicator Informs administration and/or appropriate personnel of school-related items. This means that effective communication with school

administration and relevant personnel is essential for ensuring the smooth operation of school-related activities and addressing any issues or concerns promptly. This score implies that the majority of respondents agree on the effectiveness of teachers' efforts to keep administration and relevant personnel informed about important school matters. Teachers are always encouraged to enhance communication channels between them and administration as it could further optimize the overall effectiveness of community involvement initiatives. It suggests that if teachers effectively communicate with administrators and school leaders, it can lead to improved support for students. This support can take many forms, such as targeted interventions, additional resources, or professional development for teachers, all of which can positively impact student learning outcomes.

Roxas et al. (2018) emphasized that genuine school reforms invariably commence with heightened effective communication of the school's different stakeholders, which include primarily the teachers and the school administration. Effective communication fosters a shared vision and mutual understanding, which are critical for implementing and sustaining meaningful changes. This collaboration ensures that the reforms are aligned with the needs and expectations of the entire school.

Professional growth and development are essential for teachers to enhance their knowledge, skills, and instructional practices. Continuous professional development is associated to improved student learning outcomes, as it equips teachers with the latest pedagogical strategies and content knowledge. Collaborative learning, data-driven decision-making, personalized learning, reflective practice, and effective mentorship are key components that contribute to successful professional development. By investing in high-quality professional growth and development, schools can empower teachers to enhance their skills and ultimately improve student learning experiences. Continuous investment in teachers' professional growth is a pathway to achieving educational excellence and equity. Effective strategies for professional development will empower teachers to improve their practices, ultimately benefiting students and the broader educational community.

Table 3.4. Distribution of the Teachers' Level of Performance in Terms of Professional Growth and Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Gets involved in professional associations.	3.60	0.51	Strongly Agree
Participates on district/state committees, etc.	3.51	0.53	Strongly Agree
Participates in professional workshops.	3.63	0.51	Strongly Agree
Attends professional meetings.	3.63	0.49	Strongly Agree
Keeps current in subject area.	3.67	0.48	Strongly Agree
Engages in continuing education.	3.61	0.52	Strongly Agree
Publishes research or articles in peer-reviewed journals or educational publications related to their field of expertise.	3.22	0.78	Agree
Presents at conferences or workshops on topics related to their field of expertise.	3.34	0.66	Agree
Mentors or coaches' other educators to enhance their professional growth and development.	3.39	0.65	Agree

Leads or facilitates professional learning communities or study groups focused on advancing teaching practices and pedagogy.	3.39	0.60	Agree
Overall	3.50	0.43	Strongly Agree
Legend:	3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Outstanding	1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ Satisfactory	
	2.61 – 3.40 Agree / Very Satisfactory	1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/ Poor	

Table 3.4 presents the teachers' level of performance in terms of professional growth and development with an overall mean score of 3.50 (SD=0.43), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This means that most respondents share a similar view on the effectiveness of teachers in this area. This strong agreement highlights the importance of continuous professional development in fostering a culture of learning and improvement within educational settings. This implies that continuous professional development result to improved teaching practices. Teachers who engage in ongoing learning opportunities are better equipped with the latest pedagogical strategies, content knowledge, and classroom management techniques, which can lead to enhanced student learning outcomes. It suggests that schools need to prioritize professional growth among teachers to foster a culture of continuous learning. This culture encourages teachers to seek out new knowledge and skills, promoting an environment where innovation and improvement are valued so that students can benefit to a more dynamic and engaging learning experiences.

According to Schwartz (2023), investing in professional growth and development demonstrates a commitment to lifelong learning and professional excellence, which can enhance job satisfaction, teacher morale, and overall school effectiveness.

Among the ten evaluated indicators, the highest mean score is observed in keeps current in subject area, with a mean of 3.67 (SD = 0.48) described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Outstanding. This underlines the importance of teachers staying updated with the latest developments and strategies in their respective fields, ensuring the delivery of relevant and high-quality instruction to students. The high mean score in this area reflects the proactive efforts of teachers in maintaining their subject knowledge and expertise. It implies that teachers need to be updated with recent advancements in teaching strategies and pedagogy. Moreover, the regional offices of the Department of Education also conduct the same trainings, which is specific for a teacher's subject area, on an annual basis. These programs play a crucial role in supporting teachers' professional growth and development. These programs help ensure that teachers remain effective and competent in their roles by providing them opportunities to engage in ongoing learning and staying abreast of recent advancements in teaching strategies.

The results support the claim of Mizell (2019) that professional development, stemming from externally provided activities, is merged with teachers' efforts to enhance knowledge and transform their approach to teaching, thus facilitating student support through learning. Without continuous professional growth and development, teachers face the potential of lagging behind and losing touch with the optimal practices essential for fostering student success (Schwartz, 2023).

Conversely, the lowest mean score is indicator publishes research or articles in peer-reviewed journals or educational publications related to their field of expertise, with a mean of 3.22 (SD=0.78), described as Agree and Very Satisfactory interpretation. This suggests a comparatively lower level of engagement in scholarly research among teachers. Despite being continually encouraged to conduct research, the demanding nature of teaching itself could be the reason why teachers have limited time and resources available for engaging in scholarly pursuits. Teachers often have heavy workloads, including lesson planning, grading, and extracurricular activities, which leave them with limited time to dedicate to research and writing. Additionally, the lack of incentives or recognition for scholarly publication within the DepEd system could have also contributed to the low publication rates among teachers. Unlike in higher education institutions where research and publication are often valued and rewarded, teachers within the DepEd do not receive the same level of support or encouragement to engage in research publications.

Thahir et al. (2021) emphasized that encouraging teachers to pursue research and publication opportunities can contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field and further elevate the profession. Teachers can contribute valuable insights and perspectives to the educational discourse, enriching both theory and practice, when they engage in scholarly activities. Schweikhardt (2020) added that publishing in peer-reviewed journals can enhance the credibility and reputation of educators, fostering professional recognition and career advancement opportunities within the academic community.

Table 3.5. Summary of the Level of Teachers' Performance

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Teaching and Learning Process	3.63	0.38	Outstanding
Students Outcome	3.60	0.39	Outstanding
Community Involvement	3.58	0.37	Outstanding
Professional Growth and Development	3.50	0.43	Outstanding
Overall	3.58	0.39	Outstanding

Legend: 3.41 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Outstanding
 2.61 – 3.40 Agree / Very Satisfactory
 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ Satisfactory
 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/ Poor

Table 3.5 reflects the summary of the level of teachers' performance across four domains: the teaching and learning process, students' outcome, community involvement, and professional growth and development. The overall assessment of teachers' performance across various components reveals an exceptional level of effectiveness, with an overall mean score of 3.58 (SD=0.39), interpreted as Outstanding. This collective evaluation indicates a consistently high standard maintained across teaching and learning processes, student outcomes, community involvement, and professional growth and development. It further highlights the dedication and proficiency of teachers in various aspects of their roles. However, attention to areas with slightly lower mean scores, such as professional growth and development, is crucial for sustaining and enhancing overall teaching performance levels.

According to Sarabia and Collantes (2020), effective teaching performance is crucial for ensuring that students receive high-quality education and achieve their academic goals. A teacher's performance is not only reflected in their ability to convey complex concepts in a clear and concise manner but also in their capacity to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. This includes fostering a sense of belonging among students, encouraging active participation, and providing personalized feedback that addresses individual needs (Ereje and Ambag, 2020).

Among the four dimensions of teaching performance, teaching and learning process has the highest mean of 3.63 (SD=0.38), interpreted as Outstanding. The result highlights the importance of engaging teaching strategies, positive learning environments, and continuous improvement in professional development. By recognizing and reinforcing effective teaching practices, educational institutions can further enhance student engagement, satisfaction, and academic success, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes for all learners. This implies that teachers are highly effective in their instructional methods, classroom management, and engagement strategies, leading to a superior educational experience for students. The outstanding performance in this dimension highlights the success of current teaching practices and potentially serves as a model for enhancing other areas of teaching performance to achieve similar excellence.

The result supports previous claim of Hoque et al (2020) that a teacher's performance is also influenced by their ability to adapt to diverse learning styles, incorporate technology into their teaching methods, and stay updated with the latest developments in their subject area. By doing so, teachers can ensure that their teaching practices remain relevant and engaging, ultimately leading to better student outcomes and a more fulfilling educational experience (Daly, 2022).

On the other hand, among the components of teaching performance, professional growth and development got the lowest mean of 3.50 (SD=0.43) interpreted as Outstanding. The score indicates that teachers are engaged in activities aimed at improving their skills and knowledge. This commitment to continuous improvement is essential for adapting to new educational challenges and enhancing teaching effectiveness. The result implies that while teachers are performing exceptionally well in this area, it is relatively less emphasized or prioritized compared to other components of teaching performance. This indicates that there may be opportunities for further enhancing teachers' professional growth and development initiatives to ensure continuous improvement and maintain high standards. Despite being the lowest-scoring component, the outstanding rating suggests a solid foundation upon which to build even more robust professional development programs, thereby ensuring sustained excellence in teaching performance across all dimensions.

According to Mizell (2019), ongoing professional development equips teachers with updated knowledge, skills, and best practices, fostering a culture of lifelong learning and continuous improvement. It also enhances teachers' ability to implement innovative instructional strategies, manage classrooms efficiently, and support students' academic and socio-emotional growth (Schwartz, 2023).

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between Master Teacher’s instructional supervisory skills and the teachers’ performance?

Table 4.1. Relationship Between the Master Teacher’s Instructional Supervisory Skills and Teachers’ Performance

Master Teachers’ Supervisory Skills	Teachers Performance				
	Teaching and Learning	Students’ Outcome	Community Involvement	Professional Growth and Development	Overall
	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value
Coaching	0.47	0.36	0.53	0.40	0.44
	0.030	0.078	0.000	0.034	0.035
Mentoring	S	NS	S	S	S
	0.12	0.56	0.44	0.34	0.37
Clinical Supervision	0.067	0.048	0.032	0.014	0.04
	NS	S	S	S	S
Pedagogical	0.24	0.29	0.02	0.36	0.23
	0.390	0.043	0.824	0.045	0.325
Technological	NS	S	NS	S	NS
	0.41	0.32	0.48	0.31	0.38
Evaluation	0.02	0.046	0.36	0.042	0.04
	S	S	S	S	S
Evaluation	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.05
	0.467	0.516	0.518	0.851	0.588
Evaluation	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
	0.36	0.46	0.50	0.28	0.34
Evaluation	0.008	0.031	0.000	0.02	0.01
	S	S	S	S	S

Legend: Significant at $p < .05$ alpha level

Table 4.1 shows the statistical result of the correlation analysis that tested the relationship between master teachers’ instructional supervisory skills and the teachers’ teaching performance. The result shows that there is a weak positive relationship between the variable supervisory skills in coaching and teaching performance. The r-value of 0.44 indicates a weak positive correlation between the two variables, suggesting that as the instructional supervisory skills of Master Teachers in coaching improve, there is a corresponding enhancement in teachers’ work performance. The p-value of 0.035 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant, this implies that master teachers can provide targeted feedback and modeling to help teachers improve the teaching and learning and in the same way that coaching helps teachers develop more effective, research-based instructional strategies. Therefore, the data strongly suggest that effective instructional supervision by Master Teachers in teaching and learning, community involvement and professional growth and development is associated with better performance among teachers.

The result verifies the same relationship established by previous researchers (Buagas & Ching, 2023; David et al., 2023; Ordavisa & Cañon, 2020) on the positive relationship between Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills and teachers' performance.

Meanwhile, the mentoring supervisory skill of master teachers have strong positive relationship with the teacher performance having r-value of 0.37 and statistically significant with p-value of 0.04. The results indicate that there is a positive relationship even though it was moderate in strength. Although the relationship is moderate in strength, the statistical significance underscores its reliability and suggests that enhancements in mentoring skills can lead to noticeable improvements in teaching performance. This finding highlights the importance of developing and investing in mentoring programs for master teachers, as their ability to mentor effectively plays a crucial role in elevating the overall quality of education. The results highlight some areas where master teachers may need additional training or support to strengthen their mentoring competencies, especially on developing stronger interpersonal and mentoring skills. Its implication is that school systems and policymakers should consider a more holistic approach to teacher development, where master teacher mentoring is one component alongside other supports, rather than relying on mentoring alone to drive teacher performance. Also, evaluation and refinement of master teacher mentoring programs may be needed to identify areas for improvement and ensure that mentoring is having the desired impact on teaching and learning.

Moreover, Ordanel and Dioso (2023) posited that the leadership capacity of Master Teachers is critical for improving teacher performance, as it allows MTs to set clear goals, provide guidance and support, and foster a positive learning environment. Additionally, the study found that master teachers' mentoring skills, such as co-teaching and providing guidance, are essential for developing the instructional competence of their colleagues.

Additionally, a weak positive relationship between master teachers' skills in clinical supervision with r-value of 0.23 and statistically no significant relationship with p-value of 0.325 is shown in the table. The low r-value suggests that master teachers' clinical supervision skills account for only about 5% of the variation in teacher performance this means other factors likely play a much larger role and the high p-value of 0.3255 indicates there is a 32.55% probability that the observed relationship occurred by chance. This exceeds the typical 5% threshold for statistical significance which means we cannot confidently conclude that there is a true relationship between the variables. The weak relationship and lack of statistical significance suggest that simply possessing strong clinical supervision skills may not be enough for master teachers to meaningfully impact teacher performance there are other factors, such as the quality of feedback, frequency of observations, and teachers' receptiveness to coaching, likely moderate the effectiveness of clinical supervision.

The result implies that master teachers should not overemphasize clinical supervision skills when selecting and training master teachers, these skills alone do not appear to be a key reason of improved teacher performance. Master teacher training programs may need to expand beyond just clinical supervision to include other competencies, such as

adult learning principles, emotional intelligence, and change management. Thus, it is significant that evaluating the impact of master teachers should consider multiple measures beyond just teacher performance, such as student outcomes, teacher retention, and even school culture.

The result is confirmed by previous researchers (David et al., 2023; Basilio & Bueno, 2021; Bush et al., 2017), who claimed why clinical supervision often fails to positively affect teaching performance. Oftentimes, the structured and often rigid nature of clinical supervision can stifle teacher creativity and autonomy. Teachers may feel constrained by the strict protocols and assessments, leading to a lack of innovation in their teaching methods. Moreover, they claimed that focus on compliance and adherence to standardized procedures during clinical supervision may not address the individual needs and contextual challenges faced by teachers. This can result in generic feedback that does not help teachers improve their specific areas of weakness or leverage their strengths effectively.

In pedagogical dimension, results showed that the relationship is statistically significant between master teachers' supervisory skills and teachers' performance with p-value of 0.38 and r-value of 0.04 which has strong positive relationship. This finding implies that improvements in master teachers' supervisory abilities could potentially enhance teachers' pedagogical practices and subsequently impact student learning outcomes. However, given the weak correlation, additional factors beyond supervisory skills likely influence pedagogical effectiveness, highlighting the need for comprehensive support and development strategies to optimize teaching practices in this dimension.

The result confirms the claims of Asio et al. (2018) that teaching performance can be improved through continuous professional development, effective use of technology, and regular feedback. Professional development opportunities, such as workshops and training sessions, help teachers stay updated with the latest educational practices and methodologies. Integrating technology in the classroom can enhance learning experiences and engagement. Additionally, regular feedback from peers, students, and administrators can provide valuable insights for teachers to refine their teaching strategies and address any areas of improvement.

Master teacher's supervisory skills in technological aspect has no linear relationship with the teacher's performance having an r-value of 0.053 and a p-value of 0.59 showed that statistically no significant relationship. This means that changes in master teachers' technological supervisory skills are not associated with any meaningful changes in teachers' performance.

The findings suggest that master teachers' supervisory skills in the technological aspect do not play a significant role in determining teachers' performance. These results provide valuable insights for educational leaders and policymakers to focus on a broader range of factors beyond just master teachers' technological supervisory skills when developing strategies to improve teachers' performance in the technological aspect of their work. Investing in teacher training, providing adequate technological resources, and fostering a

supportive environment for technology integration may be more effective in enhancing teachers' performance in this area.

This implies that other factors, such as teachers' own technological skills, access to technology resources, strong internet connectivity and the integration of technology into the curriculum, may be more important in shaping teachers' performance in this area. The lack of a linear relationship between the two variables suggests that improving master teachers' technological supervisory skills alone may not lead to significant improvements in teachers' performance. It also suggests more comprehensive approach that addresses various aspects of technology integration in education may be necessary to enhance teachers' performance in this domain.

Batuiguis et al. (2022) asserted that teachers need to have strong technological skills to effectively integrate technology into their teaching. This includes understanding how to use various devices, software, and online tools, as well as being able to troubleshoot issues that may arise. Without these skills, teachers may feel overwhelmed and less confident in using technology, which can limit its effectiveness in the classroom.

Lastly, the evaluation supervisory skills of master teachers with r-value of 0.034 suggests there is a linear relationship between master teachers' evaluation supervisory skills and teachers' performance. This means that changes in master teachers' evaluation supervisory skills are associated with any meaningful changes in teachers' performance. The p-value of 0.01 is well below the commonly used significance level of 0.05, indicating that the observed linear relationship between the two variables is statistically significant. This means that the finding did not occur by chance instead shows a more reliable and meaningful relationship. It also further implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that a linear relationship exists between the two variables under investigation.

The finding suggests that improvements or declines in supervisory skills are consistently associated with changes in teachers' performance. While the effect size is minimal, the consistent association implies that efforts to enhance supervisory skills are still relevant, as even small changes in these skills can impact teachers' performance. This finding underscores the importance of continuous professional development for master teachers, though it highlights that such efforts may result in modest performance gains among teachers.

These findings provide valuable insights for educational administrators and policymakers to look beyond just the evaluation of the supervisory skills of master teachers when developing strategies to improve teachers' performance. Focusing on a broader range of factors, such as creating a supportive and collaborative work environment, providing targeted professional development, and fostering effective feedback mechanisms, may be more effective in enhancing teachers' performance.

Comighud et al. (2020) explained that Master Teachers' competencies are crucial for effective supervision, as they enable them to guide and support their colleagues in delivering high-quality instruction. Specifically, master teachers' proficiency in curriculum

planning and assessment and reporting skills helps them to develop and implement effective lesson plans and evaluate student performance accurately, which in turn enhances the overall academic performance of the school. Lopez (2018) advised that to enhance the MTs instructional supervisory skills, the Department of Education may provide professional development opportunities, such as regular training sessions and workshops focused on pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, evaluation skills, and mentoring skills.

Research Question 5. Is there a significant difference in the teachers’ performance when grouped according to their characteristics?

Table 5 Test of Difference between Teachers’ Performance and Each of the Respondents’ Characteristics

Respondents Characteristics	Teachers Performance				
	Teaching and Learning	Student’s Outcome	Community Involvement	Professional Growth and Development	Overall
	t-value p-value	t-value p-value	t-value p-value	t-value p-value	t-value p-value
Sex	0.129	0.291	2.004	0.050	0.396
	0.897	0.772	0.093	0.961	0.693
	NS	S	NS	NS	NS
Highest Educational Attainment	0.815	0.786	0.790	0.444	0.702
	0.016	0.002	0.000	0.022	0.002
	S	S	S	S	S
Teaching Experience	0.729	0.91	0.647	0.850	0.629
	0.04	0.072	0.018	0.02	0.03
	S	S	S	S	S
Ethnicity	0.344	0.460	0.502	0.517	0.409
	0.913	0.838	0.807	0.796	0.853
	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Attitude Towards Supervision	24.004	22.708	22.165	34.898	23.216
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	S	S	S	S	S

Legend: Significant at $p < .05$ alpha level

Table 5 reflects the statistical result of the test of difference conducted to determine the significant difference in the teachers’ performance when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, ethnicity and attitudes towards supervision. The table presents the results of a t-test conducted to determine if there is a significant difference in the teachers’ performance based on gender. The sample consisted of 65 male teachers and 351 female teachers. The t-value is 0.396, with and the significance level (p-value) is .069. The results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the performance of teachers based on sex, as the p-value of .693

is well above the common threshold of .05. The result suggests that gender does not play a significant role in determining teacher performance within the context of local of the study. It further implies that the teachers' excellent performance, presented in the previous tables, was attained regardless of the teachers' gender preferences. Therefore, efforts to improve teacher performance should focus on factors other than gender, as both male and female teachers perform at similar levels. The division can create fair and unbiased policies and programs that support teacher development and performance enhancement without regard to gender.

The same result was established in the study of Graham et al. (2020), who posited that gender does not significantly influence teachers' teaching performance because it is not a determinant of their instructional style or classroom management. Accordingly, it does not necessarily dictate the type or quality of instruction that occurs in the classroom, nor does it affect their ability to manage and engage students effectively. Therefore, performance outcomes are more likely influenced by individual skills, experience, and professional development opportunities rather than gender. Contrary to the result, Sarabia and Collantes (2020) found that gender and position emerged as positive predictors of teaching performance, suggesting that female teachers and those in higher positions tended to have better teaching performance.

The t-test results on the teachers' performance when grouped according to highest educational attainment. The t-value from the ANOVA test is 0.702 and the significance level (p-value) is 0.002. The results indicate that there is a statistically significant difference in the teachers' performance based on their highest educational attainment, as the p-value of 0.002 is below the common significance threshold of .05. This suggests that the level of academic qualification whether having MA units, an MA degree, PhD units, or a PhD degree significantly affect teachers' performance. The p-value well below the common significance threshold that this difference is not due to chance. This implies that the level of academic qualification—whether having MA units, an MA degree, PhD units, or a PhD degree—has a significant effect on teachers' performance. Therefore, higher educational attainment among teachers is associated with better performance, highlighting the importance of encouraging advanced studies and continuous professional development for educators to enhance their teaching effectiveness and overall performance.

The results affirm the findings Balanquit et al. (2023) that teaching performance do not necessarily hinges on the teachers' highest educational attainment. While advanced degrees provide theoretical knowledge, practical skills such as classroom management, instructional techniques, and the ability to engage and motivate students play a crucial role in teaching efficacy. However, according to Pido et al. (2023) teachers with advanced degrees are often thought to have superior teaching competencies that positively impact student learning. This enhanced teaching ability is expected to lead to higher performance and increased school productivity. Pama (2023) added that ongoing professional development, teaching experience, and personal attributes such as enthusiasm, adaptability, and empathy are critical in shaping a teacher's performance.

Further, the comparison of teachers' performance when grouped according to teaching experience. As reflected in the table, the teacher respondents were grouped into five categories according to their years of teaching experience. The t-value obtained from the analysis is 0.629, and the significance level (p-value) is 0.03. Since the p-value is below the conventional threshold of 0.05, the differences in teachers' performance across the different experience groups are statistically significant. This implies that, based on this data, teaching experience have a significant impact on teachers' performance ratings. This underscores the value of accumulated teaching experience in enhancing teaching effectiveness, classroom management skills, instructional strategies, and overall professional competence. The findings also suggest that educational institutions and policymakers should consider strategies to support and retain experienced teachers, as their accumulated expertise contributes positively to educational outcomes.

The result coincides with the findings of Ekaterini et al. (2022) and Irvine (2019) who both suggested that teacher experience significantly affects teacher effectiveness, primarily during the initial years of a teacher's career. They argued that improvement generally occurs over the first 4 to 5 years but note that this is an average, with some less experienced teachers improving much more rapidly than others. Pama (2023) elucidated that while experience matters, more is not always better. The relationship between teaching experience and effectiveness is nonlinear, with the greatest gains in the first few years. After that, factors like the teaching environment, subject area, and individual teacher characteristics become more important in determining the effectiveness than total years of experience alone.

On another note, the t-test result of the comparison on the teachers' performance when grouped according to ethnicity. The study categorizes teachers into eight ethnic groups: Bukidnon, Higaunon, Manobo, Matigsalog, Talaandig, Tigwahanon, Umayamnon, and a category for those identifying as none of the above. The t-value obtained from the analysis is 0.439 and a significance level (p-value) of 0.853. Given that the p-value is significantly higher than the conventional threshold of 0.05, the differences in teachers' performance across different ethnic groups are not statistically significant. The study cannot fully determine the effect of ethnicity because majority of the respondents are not part of the Bukidnon tribe. This result implies that teacher performance does not significantly differ based on ethnicity within the respondents of this study. The similarity in performance across ethnic groups suggests that factors other than ethnicity are playing a more critical role in influencing teacher effectiveness.

The results align with the findings of Steinberg and Sartain (2020) that ethnicity does not significantly influence their performance because the professional environment, training, and support systems provided to teachers are designed to be inclusive and standardized across all ethnic groups. This standardization ensures that all teachers have access to the same resources, professional development opportunities, and support networks, thereby creating a level playing field where individual performance is more influenced by these professional factors rather than ethnic background (Joshi & James, 2022).

Finally, the t-test result of the comparison on the teachers' performance when they are grouped according to their attitude towards supervision. The study categorizes teachers into four groups based on their attitudes: very negative, negative, positive, and very positive. The t-value is 23.216 and the significance level (p-value) is 0.000, indicating that the differences in teachers performance are statistically significant. The results imply that a teacher's attitude towards supervision has a significant impact on their performance. Teachers with very positive attitudes towards supervision perform markedly better than those with negative or very negative attitudes. This suggests that a constructive and receptive attitude towards supervision can enhance teacher performance, potentially due to greater openness to feedback, willingness to improve, and a more collaborative relationship with supervisors. Teachers who have positive attitude towards supervision, they are more likely to feel confident in their abilities and more receptive to feedback and guidance from supervisors.

Buagas and Ching (2023) posited that the teachers' positive attitudes toward instructional supervision are positively correlated with their job performance. When teachers view instructional supervision as a tool for professional growth and improving student performance, it leads to better teaching outcomes. Similarly, Echeche (2022) asserted that the impact of positive attitudes on supervision can be seen in the way teachers approach their work. Teachers who have a positive view of supervision are more likely to be proactive in seeking feedback and support, and to be open to new ideas and strategies. This can lead to a more collaborative and dynamic teaching environment, where teachers feel empowered to take ownership of their professional development and to make a positive impact on student learning. Moreover, Dingal (2023) expounded that effective supervision practices by master teachers and supervisors can improve teachers' perceptions of supervision, which in turn enhances their job performance. Felisilda and Malaga (2019) added that the relationship between instructional supervisory practice and teacher job performance is mediated by teachers' attitudes, meaning that positive attitudes help translate effective supervision into improved teaching. Teachers who perceive supervision as meeting their professional needs, fostering collaboration and trust, and providing support and guidance tend to have more positive attitudes.

Research Question 6. Based on the findings of the study, what instructional supervisory plan can be designed?

Table 6. Matrix of School Instructional Supervisory Plan

Year 1							
Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Funds	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Professional Growth and Development	Publishes research or articles in peer-reviewed journals or educational publications related to	Publishes research or articles in peer-reviewed journals Seminar workshops on crafting action research	Whole year round	Master Teacher School Principal Division Office Key Officials	MOOE PTA Fund	100,000.00	Publish research on international journals Completion of online courses Annual professional development evaluation

	their field of expertise.	Workshops, seminars, and online courses.					
Mentoring on Conduct action research	Conduct in-depth studies or action research	Provide training on action research methodologies. Organize action research symposiums to share findings. Increase teacher participation in action research projects. Improve instructional practices based on research findings.	Whole year round	Master Teacher School Principal Division Office Key Officials	MOOE PTA Fund	100,000.00	Research-based instructional materials Innovative teaching strategies embedded in the lesson exemplar Certificate of trainings Improve students data by applying research findings Completed and implemented action research

Year 2							
Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Funds	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Professional Growth and Development	Presents conferences or workshops on the topics related to their field of expertise Equip teachers with the skills to analyze student data Use data to set informed and realistic expectations for the students	Data-Driven Instruction Planning Session Group discussions and activities. Hands-on exercises and simulation Peer-to-peer sharing and feedback.	Throughout academic year	Master Teacher School Principal All teachers (grouped according to their field)	MOOE PTA Fund	50,000.00	Sample data sets Lesson plan Lesson study results
Supervisory skills on mentoring teachers	Conduct echo seminars in content and self-difficulties	collaborative planning and co-teaching Engage teachers in problem-solving and discussion					Reflective journal Teachers portfolio Students progress report chart

		Encourage teachers to reflect on their experiences, challenges, and growth					
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Year 3							
Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Funds	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Professional Growth and development	Assist teachers to enhance professional growth and development Facilitate professional learning communities on advancing teaching practices and pedagogy	Learning action cell sessions In-service training on content and pedagogy Demonstration teaching to enhance teaching practices Class monitoring and evaluation Lesson planning for effective teaching strategies	Throughout academic year	Master Teachers School Principal All teachers (grouped according to major) Division Office Key Officials	MOOE PTA LGU	100,000.00	Post training report and evaluation Teacher-made lesson plans Class observation rating Instructional plan
Supervisory skills on mentoring teachers	Evaluate teacher-made tests and interpret results	Training for teachers in developing high-quality Reviewing and providing feedback on teacher-made tests Analyzing test results	Throughout academic year	Master Teachers School Principal All teachers Division Office personnel	MOOE PTA LGU	100,000.00	Post training report Quarterly test analysis result Test questions with table of specification

Conclusions

From the findings and discussions outlined, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The characteristics of Master Teachers and teachers within the Division of Valencia City demonstrate a diverse spectrum, encompassing gender imbalance, strong educational commitment, mid-career stability, and ethnic diversity. Moreover, the positive attitudes towards instructional supervision underscore its perceived importance in

enhancing teaching practices and fostering professional growth within the educational community.

2. The excellence of Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills in pedagogical dimension, and across various domains, proves their profound ability to guide and enhance teaching practices. This mastery not only ensures effective delivery of curriculum but also fosters continuous professional growth among educators.

3. The excellence of teachers' teaching performance in the area of teaching and learning process, and across various dimensions, reflect a commitment to excellence in education. It further affirms their significant contributions to student success and the broader educational community.

4. The significant relationship between Master Teachers' instructional supervisory skills and teachers' teaching performance emphasizes the crucial role of effective instructional supervision in enhancing teaching quality and student learning outcomes.

5. The significant difference of the teachers' performance when grouped according to highest educational attainment and teaching experience underscores the impact of advanced knowledge and seasoned practice on classroom outcomes. This differentiation highlights the important contributions that diverse educational backgrounds and extensive teaching tenure bring to the educational landscape, shaping both student achievement and institutional success.

6. Based on the conclusions established, this study proposed the Theory of Supervisory Impact on Teaching Excellence. This theory posits that consistent and effective instructional supervision by Master Teachers is fundamental in enhancing teaching performance, strengthening educational attainment and teaching experience to increase student success and overall educational improvement.

Recommendations

Based on the relevant findings and conclusions drawn, this study proposed the following recommendations:

1. Master Teachers may continuously refine and expand their instructional supervisory skills, particularly in mentoring and supporting less experienced educators.

2. The teachers could embrace opportunities for professional growth and development, such as participating in workshops, conferences, and continuing education programs to stay update with recent advancements in teaching methodologies, technology integration, and subject area knowledge.

3. The Division may facilitate the adoption and implementation of this study's proposed School Instructional Supervisory Plan by providing comprehensive training for school leaders and instructional supervisors. This can be done through workshops and seminars that focus on the components and benefits of the plan, as well as practical strategies for effective implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to commencing the study, the researcher undergone an ethics review and earned clearance from the office of the Graduate Studies spearheaded by the research

coordinator. After which a permit letter to conduct the study signed by the dean was given to the researcher. The researcher forwarded it to the Division of Valencia City Schools Division Superintendent for endorsement to the school principals to gather necessary data for the study. The research participants were informed of the purpose and nature of the study, emphasizing that their participation is purely voluntary and does not, therefore, include any monetary remuneration. The researcher also stressed that the participants had the choice to refrain from answering questions that made them feel uneasy. Furthermore, they were assured that the data gathered from their participation was handled with strict adherence to ethical considerations in research. This included maintaining confidentiality, ensuring anonymity where appropriate, and obtaining informed consent prior to participation. Finally, the participants were asked to sign a consent letter, signifying their intention to participate in the study.

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